

**An investigation into the adoption of the Climate Change Sustainable
Development Goal by the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare**

by

Geraldine Mupandanyama

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Supervisor: F. Magaa

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Declaration

I, Geraldine Mupandanyama, do hereby declare that this dissertation is the result of my investigation and research and that this has not been submitted in part or full for any degree or for any other degree to any other University.

28/02/2022

G. Mupandanyama

Date

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Abstract

As the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare expands and new entrants come, there is need to adhere to global greenhouse gas emissions eradication goals by all existing players and new players in this industry. The climate change crisis cannot afford to be treated as another man's problem because everyone is suffering from its negative effects and everyone has been contributing to the problem directly or indirectly.

This dissertation will review and analyse the extent to which the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare is adopting the climate change Sustainable Development Goal (SDG). Using a qualitative research approach and data from a small sample of haphazardly selected environmental management practitioners in the industry, the researcher investigated the initiatives organisations implement to reduce or minimise greenhouse gas emissions. The researcher found that while the organisations did not have a standalone blueprint on the climate change SDG, they somewhat indirectly addressed the goal through their voluntary environmental management and sustainability initiatives.

The climate change SDG is not a top priority for the industry which is inundated with the numerous challenges of operating their businesses under the austere economic condition that businesses in Zimbabwe operate in. Additionally, the level of enforcement from the regulatory authorities as far as ensuring businesses comply with the national climate change policies and laws was minimal.

The Government is encouraged to roll out initiatives to incentivise industry to prioritise climate change mitigation projects. Additionally, stringent measures are necessary to govern the adherence to the laws and policies of the land pertaining to the climate change SDG.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title page	i
Declaration	ii
Acknowledgements	iii
Abstract	iv
Abbreviations	3
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION	5
1.1 Introduction	5
1.2 Background to the problem	5
1.3 Problem statement	6
1.4 Aim of the study	7
1.5 Objectives of the study	7
1.6 Research questions	7
1.7 Significance of the study	8
1.8 Chapter Outlines	9
1.8.1 Chapter 1	9
1.8.2 Chapter 2	9
1.8.3 Chapter 3	9
1.8.4 Chapter 4	10
1.8.5 Chapter 5	10
1.9 Conclusion	10
CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW	11
2.1 Introduction	11
2.2 Climate change and global warming	11
2.3 Climate change causes	14
2.4 The SDGs and their benefits	16
2.5 Zimbabwe climate change response strategy	19
2.6 The manufacturing industry's contribution to climate change	21
2.7 Climate Change Sustainable Development Goal strategies	24
2.8 Conclusion	29
CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	31
3.1 Introduction	31
3.2 Research Design	31
3.2.1 Exploratory design	32
3.2.2 Explanatory design	32
3.2.3 Descriptive Design	32
3.2.4 Causal-comparative Design	33
3.2.5 Correlational Design	33
3.3 Research Philosophy	34
3.4 Research Strategy	35
3.4.1 Positivist Research Strategy	35
3.4.2 Phenomenological research strategies	35
3.5 Target population	37
3.5.1 Sampling	37
3.5.2 Kinds of sampling	38

3.6 The Research Instrument.....	40
3.6.1 Questionnaire construction.....	42
3.6.2 Interviews.....	42
3.7 Pilot Study.....	43
3.8 Conduct of Interviews.....	44
3.9 Data Analysis.....	45
3.10 Validity and Reliability.....	47
3.10.1 Credibility.....	47
3.10.2 Transferability.....	47
3.10.3 Dependability.....	48
3.10.4 Confirmability.....	48
3.11 Limitations of the Study.....	49
3.12 Elimination of Bias.....	50
3.13 Ethical Considerations.....	50
3.13.1 Ensuring participants have given informed consent.....	51
3.13.2 Ensuring no harm comes to participants.....	51
3.13.3 Ensuring confidentiality and anonymity.....	51
3.13.4 Ensuring that permission is obtained.....	51
3.14 Conclusion.....	52
CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS, DISCUSSION, AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS.....	53
4.1 Introduction.....	53
4.2 Thematic Analysis of Qualitative Data.....	54
4.2.1 Identification of themes.....	54
4.2.2 Core Themes.....	55
4.2.3 Core Themes Analysed.....	56
4.3 Conclusion.....	66
CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	67
5.1 Findings from the Study.....	67
5.1.1 Introduction.....	67
5.1.2 Findings from the Study.....	67
5.1.2.1 Findings from the Literature Review.....	67
5.1.2.2 Findings from the Primary Research.....	69
5.1.4 Conclusions.....	74
5.2 Recommendations.....	75
5.3 Conclusion.....	77
BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	78
APPENDICES.....	82
Appendix A.....	82
Appendix B.....	84
Appendix C.....	85
Appendix D.....	88

Abbreviations

AfDB	- African Development Bank
°C	- Degrees Celsius
CO ₂	- Carbon Dioxide
ESG	- Environmental, Social and Governance
GgCO ₂ eq	- Giga tonnes of CO ₂ equivalent
GHG	- Green House Gas
GoZ	- Government of Zimbabwe
GRI	- Global Reporting Initiatives
INDC	- Intended Nationally Determined Contribution
LEDS	- Low Greenhouse Gas Emission Development Strategy
MtCO ₂ e	- Metric tons of carbon dioxide equivalent
NCCRS	- National Climate Change Response Strategy
NCP	- National Climate Policy
SDG	- Sustainable Development Goal
SO ₂	- Sulfur dioxide
UNFCCC Change	- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

UN - United Nations

ZNCC - Zimbabwe's National Climate Change

ZSE - Zimbabwe Securities and Exchange

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

This chapter is devoted to the background of the study and the research problem under investigation. It will also cover the objectives of the research and the questions it seeks to answer. The significance of the study will be highlighted in this chapter.

This introduction is very brief, more introductory remarks should be added.

1.2 Background to the problem

At the United Nations (UN) Climate change conference held in Paris in 2015, member states deliberated on strict measures that should be taken in their countries to manage and reduce the negative practices that have been leading to climate change problems, with a target of keeping the temperature changes to below 2°C (Dhlakama, Dhliwayo & Murombo 2019:52). The action steps required for addressing the climate change problem demand the active participation of the agricultural manufacturing industry, being a significant player in the manufacturing industry in Zimbabwe.

As the manufacturing industry in Harare expands, there is need to adhere to global CO₂ emissions eradication by all existing players and new players in this industry. Bhada-Tata, Freire, Hoornewerg, Lee, and Yeun (2011) state that most of the greenhouse gas emissions are attributable to cities, and with the cities in developing countries expected to expand in the coming years, it is important that developing countries factor in the minimisation or eradication of emissions in their development plans. In order for the emissions to be managed, the emissions must be recognised and measured to set clear targets of how to mitigate them.

Changes in weather patterns are affecting production of food, which adds to an increase in poverty (Stoner & Wankel 2012:4). Unless corporations adopt the appropriate mindset for understanding the climate change risks, their attempts at mitigating climate change concerns will be ineffective (Stoner & Wankel 2012:6). In addressing the ways the manufacturing industry in Harare can manage the risks and

consequences of climate change there is need to focus on finding ways to manufacture without contributing to global warming.

The consequences of climate change on humans and animal species are numerous. Climate change has resulted in heat waves, flooding, droughts and respiratory diseases as a result of polluted air (Brazier 2017:78). Most industrial activities depend on regular supplies of water and electricity, which are disrupted by climate change. Zimbabwe's industry is dependent on human labour and productivity will be affected as climate change takes its toll on human health. Moreover, most industry relies on agricultural raw materials which are climate-sensitive (Brazier 2017:76).

The proposed research study aims to assess the willingness and success of the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare to mitigate the causes of climate change in the daily operations of the businesses.

1.3 Problem statement

The problem of global warming caused by greenhouse gas emissions has gone unsolved by both local authorities and the international community; even though attempts are being made to combat the problem. According to Dhlakama *et al.* (2019:52) climate change is not only an environmental problem but a larger challenge surpassing disciplinary boundaries and borders of knowledge. As a result of the situation becoming unmanageable, the livelihoods of current and future generations are threatened by disruptive changes in the climate conditions resulting in disasters such as floods, wildfires and droughts. In addition, climate change is a great threat to human health.

The study seeks to investigate the extent to which the SMMEs in Harare's agricultural manufacturing industry are addressing the critical climate change problem, and what is being done to reduce or mitigate the impact caused by manufacturing businesses on climate change. The findings will be useful in proposing the strategies that government and policy makers can implement towards

the active participation of the agricultural manufacturing industry in eradicating business practices that add to climate change.

1.4 Aim of the study

The aim of this study is to investigate the efforts the manufacturing industry in Harare is making towards the achievement of the climate change Sustainable Development Goal (SDG). The researcher shall utilise the interview method to gather information from key representatives of the agricultural manufacturing businesses. The researcher will make recommendations of the practices that the agricultural manufacturing businesses can introduce in their operations to reduce the impact on climate change. The aspired end result of the study is that the manufacturing industry in Harare and the regulatory authorities in Zimbabwe will implement the proposed recommendations.

1.5 Objectives of the study

The research objectives are as follow:

- To determine factors of implementing the climate change Sustainable Development Goal by the manufacturing industry in Harare;
- To investigate the adoption of the climate change Sustainable Development Goal by the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare; and
- To recommend a strategy that can improve the adoption of the climate change Sustainable Development Goal by the manufacturing industry in Harare.

1.6 Research questions

The research questions are as follows:

- What are factors of implementing the climate change Sustainable Development Goal by the manufacturing industry in Harare?

- How is the adoption of the climate change Sustainable Development Goal by the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare?
- What is the strategy that can improve the adoption of the climate change Sustainable Development Goal by the manufacturing industry in Harare?

1.7 Significance of the study

The research will fill in an essential gap by contributing to the knowledge and literature on the environmental management performance of the manufacturing industry in Harare, while exploring the effectiveness of the climate change SDG in reducing global warming. The research will be of interest to government, environmental protection bodies, businesses and the public who are interested in combating climate change. The results of this study may influence the formulation of policies to enhance the efficiencies of the environmental, social and governance (ESG) of the manufacturing industry in Harare, and Zimbabwe at large.

The study will also be useful to businesses, whose knowledge of the relationship between climate change and the day-to-day business practices is crucial for coming up with strategies that will combat climate change.

It is also desired that the research will contribute to the debate and interventions required by developing countries in playing their part to put the climate change SDG ahead of economic advancements.

Furthermore, it is hoped that the manufacturing industry and government will work together to expedite the implementation of good environmental practices that not only make the businesses profitable but that sustain the livelihoods of the communities around them while securing the safety of future generations.

The findings of this research may benefit other scholars in that scholars may build on it to look at other aspects of how the private sector and government can work together to enhance the adoption of other SDGs by African countries. The research will also contribute to an increased understanding of the current challenges the

manufacturing industry in Harare is facing in the attempt to achieve the objectives of the Paris Agreement to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in order to limit global warming to below 2°C.

1.8 Chapter Outlines

1.8.1 Chapter 1

This chapter is devoted to the background of the study and the research problem under investigation. It will also cover the objectives of the research and the questions it seeks to answer. The significance of the study as well as the scope, limitations and organisation of the study will be highlighted in this chapter.

1.8.2 Chapter 2

This chapter will provide the review of the literature and theories that frame the research topic and questions. Consideration is given to the contribution of businesses to climate change which is resulting in global warming. What climate change is and the negative effects thereof are dealt with next. An overview of what the goals the Zimbabwean government has set as mitigation measures will be provided in order to assess whether the agricultural manufacturing industry has adopted the goal sufficiently. A critical analysis of existing literature will be conducted to identify gaps in literature as well as any lack of consensus in the findings so far.

1.8.3 Chapter 3

This chapter will cover the chosen research philosophy and draw a comparison with alternative philosophies, while justifying the relevance of the chosen philosophy. An outline of the research strategies including the research methodologies will be given. Next research instruments that have been utilised to achieve the goal will be justified. The research design, target population, sample design, data collection methods, and data analysis methods of the study will be discussed and reasons for choosing the design will be given.

1.8.4 Chapter 4

This chapter will present the findings of the study, analyse the results and discuss the findings in detail. The data will be presented in diagrams and graphs and an interpretation of the data will be provided.

1.8.5 Chapter 5

The summary and conclusions of the study will be made in this chapter. Remarks will be made regarding the overall adoption of the climate change SDG by the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare. Recommendations of how to move forward in terms of international best practice for the adoption of the climate change SDG will be made.

1.9 Conclusion

This chapter has given the background to the study and has spelt out the research problem along with the research objectives and the questions derived from the objectives. The aim of the study and its significance is discussed along with the structure of the dissertation.

The next chapter reviews the literature that is relevant to the study. The literature review is expected to give readers an insight into the theoretical framework of the subject under study in view of unpacking concepts that may assist in the solving of the problem at hand.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development adopted in September 2015 was underpinned by 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and 169 targets which are meant to be integrated, indivisible and collectively support a development agenda balancing the economic, social and environmental dimensions of sustainability. The climate change SDG, which is SDG number 13 states “take urgent action to combat climate change and its impact” (United Nations, 2015) will be the focus of this study.

This chapter traces the origin of climate change and the role of the manufacturing industry through a review of literature in the following areas: definition and theories of climate change and global warming; causes of climate change; introduction to and benefits of the SDG; Zimbabwe’s National Climate Change response strategy; the manufacturing industry’s contribution to climate change; and the climate change SDG strategies.

2.2 Climate change and global warming

Climate change has attracted a lot of attention and has been a subject of many debates because of its impact on human and animal life all over the world. It has significant impact on human health, food supply, weather patterns and biodiversity. In order to fully understand the impact and the ways to control it a review is necessary.

Climate change is defined as the long-term change over decades in the Earth’s climate caused by the release of greenhouse gases that trap heat in the atmosphere (Brazier, 2017:2). Most studies describing the climate system have shown that the very high changes recorded in the past century have been mainly caused by human activities.

Scientists explain that global warming is responsible for climate change. The gases in the earth’s atmosphere trap heat, causing temperatures in the atmosphere to rise and form what is referred to as greenhouse gas. The hot atmosphere keeps the planet about 15°C warmer than it would have been (Brazier, 2017:6). Brazier points out that

research is showing that human activities are causing the excessive build up of the greenhouse gases in the atmosphere.

Dunlap (2013:692) states that the complex nature of human-caused or anthropogenic global warming and uncertainties in the risks it poses make it challenging for the layman to fully comprehend the causes, perceive the impacts, and take actions that will help alleviate future warming. This complexity has made formulating and implementing measures that might be effective in limiting the degree and impact of continued warming more difficult for policy makers. Therefore, there has been a policy stalemate as well as lack of consensus between the scientific view and that of the layman.

Some sceptics, who Dunlap (2013:694) purports that comprises of a group of conservatives, fossil fuel industrialists, contrarian scientists, politicians and sceptical bloggers allege that “climate scientists are “alarmists” who exaggerate the degree and threat of global warming to enhance their status, funding, and influence with policy makers.”

Lever-Tracy (2010:164) cites Smith (2006), a prominent climate sceptic, who argued that even regulations designed to combat global warming inevitably trample on individual economic liberty, violate the sanctity of the self-regulating capitalist market, and lead towards ‘ecosocialist’ tyranny and neo-pagan nature-worship. Lever-Tracy (2010:164) also quotes conservative journalist Brennan (2009) who wrote, “the real purpose behind the global warming movement is the establishment of a world socialist order under the control of the United Nations”.

The 2009 “climategate” controversy, which involved the theft and publication of a sample of emails from leading climate scientists who were accused of pushing a non-existent climate change agenda, contributed to a wide downturn in public belief in and concern about climate change (Weart, 2011:48). Even now these doubts are prevalent in some, as noted in the election campaigns of the former US president Donald Trump, who had led to the recently reversed withdrawal of the USA from the Paris agreement.

Weart (2011:49) who cites American Psychological Association (2009) states that Psychologists studying how citizens reacted to warnings of climate change found that the more harmful and costly global warming was said to be, the more some people insisted it was not a real problem. Even among people who believed global warming was real, the majority gave many reasons to avoid doing anything. They claimed that the danger was remote in time and space and would not affect them personally, or that any attempts to mitigate the problem would be expensive and ineffective. Some believed it would be up to other people to handle the problem, while some trusted scientists would come up with a technical solution.

As public concern about the global economy rises, concern about the environment drops. An international survey identified limitations that can hinder public understanding to be the levels of acquiescence, different cultural interpretations of global warming and varying socioeconomic and educational levels of the people (Chen, Lackner & Suzuki 2017:185). Will (2009) as cited by Chen *et al.* (2017:185) states that US audiences who believe anthropogenic global warming is negligible and over-hyped tend to be white males who are Republican, individualist, religious, and rely on radio as their main source of news.

Monkelbaan (2019:5) cites the WWF (2012) which declared that climate change and sustainable energy are crucial because carbon dioxide emissions from power generation, transport, households, and industry play a dominant role in humanity's ecological footprint. Therefore, by addressing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, a crucial opportunity for increasing the chances of sustaining the planet's bio-capacity is created.

Businesses depend on the environment for their sustenance. Agriculture manufacturers are at a high risk of faltering supply of agricultural products from parts of the world that are hit by increased occurrences of drought or storms that lower crop yields (Kolk & Pinkse (2009:93). Sectors such as agriculture, food processing, fishery and forestry all depend on raw materials obtained in the natural environment which are vulnerable to changing weather patterns.

Climate change regulation is both viewed as a business risk and an opportunity depending on the industry and country in which the business operates in (Kolk & Pinkse 2009:93). According to an Ernst & Young (2008) study cited by Kolk and Pinkse (2009:94) businesses that are large emitters of carbon, such as oil, gas, automotive and utilities often view climate regulation as a risk to their operations. This view is derived from the fact that measures such as greenhouse gas emission caps have a negative impact on the production capacity and ultimately profitability of these businesses.

On the other hand, “strict regulation favour companies that have already started to take into account of climate change in a relatively early phase and potentially crowd out companies that show a poor record with regard to emissions reductions” (Kolk & Pinkse, 2009:94). Adoption of climate change mitigation strategies can give a business competitive advantage, as consumers favour such businesses. The Agriculture manufacturing industry usually produces consumer goods such as processed food for which there are many players in the market. Therefore, businesses that are known for good environmental practice can attract more environmentally conscious customers. Other opportunities exist for financing businesses that facilitate emissions trading activities or finance carbon offset projects.

2.3 Climate change causes

Though the climate is governed by natural influences, human activities have an impact on the climate as well. Human induced climate change is directly linked to the amount of fossil fuels burned, aerosol releases, land alteration from agriculture and deforestation according to Donev, Hanania and Pomerantz (2018).

Dhlakama *et al.* (2019:15) outline the main anthropogenic factors of climate change as GHGs, aerosols due to pollution emissions and changes in land use. This notion is supported by Chen *et al.*(2017:8) who state that the main impact that humans exert on the climate is via the emission of GHG and deforestation. The natural causes of climate change highlighted by Dhlakama *et al.* (2019:15) are volcanic eruptions which result in the injection of small aerosol particles into the atmosphere, continental

drift, changes in the earth's orbit, and variations in the intensity of solar. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC 2013:17) report asserts that human factors have been the biggest causes of climate change since the mid twentieth century.

The GHG most commonly produced by human activities is CO₂ accounting for 76% of total anthropogenic GHG emissions in 2010 with the majority coming from burning fossil fuels such as oil, coal, and natural gas for energy, as well as deforestation (Dhlakama *et al.*, 2019:17). Deforestation results in the accumulation of CO₂ in the atmosphere when trees, which naturally capture this gas during the process of photosynthesis in plants, are cut down.

Chen *et al.*, (2017:12) support this by stating that the burning of fossil fuels such as coal, oil, and gas and the clearing of forests are the major source of GHG emissions. Donev *et al.* (2018) further explain that all sources of energy have some impact on the environment, however fossil fuels have a more harmful impact on the environment because they have to be extracted from the ground.

Ocean acidification due to human activity is also a notable factor that is related to anthropogenic climate change. Cornwall (2020) defines ocean acidification as the “oceanic pH decrease and associated changes in chemical speciation in dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) that occurs as a result of absorption of atmospheric carbon dioxide”. Excessive emissions of CO₂ by humans result in too much absorption of the CO₂ by the ocean leading to too much acidity in the ocean.

Chen *et al.* (2017:384) cite that approximately 92% of organic chemical products are derived from oil and gas. Fertilisers manufactures derive both raw materials and energy requirements from petroleum, making it both a heavy emitter of GHG and also highly dependent on fossil fuels. Therefore, reducing GHG emissions in an industry that is so heavily dependent on fossil fuels presents a significant challenge.

A primary product for most packaging used by agriculture manufacturing industry is plastic, which is produced from petrochemicals. Plastics consumption has increased

with gross domestic product per capita and worldwide demand for plastics is expected to rise rapidly as the average wealth increases, particularly in emerging economies (Chen *et al.*, 2017:384). Chen *et al.* (2017:386) further explain that though petrochemical products do not dominate the fossil industries, the products account for a significant share of the fossil resources. Post-consumer plastic waste is also increasingly being identified as a huge cause for climate change.

There have been heated debates on the question whether humanity can really ‘break’ the planet. Brook, Ellis and Perring (2013) as cited by Monkelbaan (2019:8) suggested that while human society modifies and changes the dynamics of local and regional ecosystems, the collective impact of all this on a planetary scale is too often overstated.

2.4 The SDGs and their benefits

The SDGs were developed following the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development in 2012 as a build up to the previously adopted Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) of September 2010. According to Griggs, McCollum, Nilsson and Visbeck (2021:19) the SDGs provide a more holistic and integrated approach to development than the MDGs, and equally apply to all countries poor, middle-income and rich. Griggs *et al.* (2021:19) further state that the SDGs promote human dignity and prosperity while safeguarding the earth’s vital biophysical processes and ecosystem services.

Crowther, Moyeen and Seifi (2018:159) cite Brundtland (1987) who defined sustainable development as “Development which meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”

A member of the audience at a public forum on ‘Africa and Sustainable Development Agendas’ at the University of Western Australia on Africa Day held on 25 May 2018, called the SDGs ‘suspicious development goals’ because the UN 2030 Agenda and African Union (AU) Agenda 2063 were endorsed in the same year, 2015, and this coincidence raises questions about whose agenda they are. Mickler and Ramutsindela

(2020:2) cited in (Hajer *et al.*, 2015) state that some people see the SDGS as the illusion that top-down steering by governments and intergovernmental organisations alone can address global problems. Other critics state that the SDGs expand the reach, scope, and influence of the aid industry and that they act as a veneer for failures to achieve meaningful and binding multilateral agreements (Mickler & Ramutsindela, 2020:2).

However, the SDGs are not legally binding but provide a globally endorsed normative framework for development (Griggs *et al.*, 2021:19). The call for SDGs is the way to move to a new global agenda that engages the world community, including governments, businesses, scientists, leaders of civil society, NGOs, and students all over the world (Sachs, 2015:484).

SDGs are action-oriented, aspirational, global in nature and universally applicable to all countries while considering different national realities, capacities and levels of development in respecting national policies and priorities (UNGA, 2012:43).

The goals are interlinked. They recognise that ending poverty and inequality go hand-in-hand with strategies that support sustainable economic growth, peace, and justice. At the same time they address fundamental social needs, including education, health, social protection, and job opportunities while also tackling climate change and enhancing environmental protection (Griggs *et al.*, 2021:20).

Some researchers argue that the linkages between the different goals and targets are both implicit and explicit therefore the SDGs are very closely integrated with social and economic issues and there are no indicators for environmental targets (Monkelbaan, 2019:4). Promoters of the SDGs argue that the fact that they are interlinked opens perspectives for integrated and more effective implementation across different sectors in the longer term.

According to Monkelbaan (2019:4), there is a strong interlink between climate change (SDG 13) and sustainable energy (SDG 7). SDG 13 undertakes to take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts while SDG 7 addresses the main culprit for

climate change, by aiming to ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all.

Climate change also has economic (SDG 16) and sociopolitical (SDG 17) impacts besides the environmental effects. Taking action on climate change will impact the ways energy is used and organise industries due to the linkages between climate change and sustainable energy. Energy use is connected to many other issues that humans rely on other than industry, such as food production and the distribution and use of water. Monkelbaan (2019:5) also cites Hawken (2017) who supports this notion by making reference to Project Drawdown, which ranks the 100 most promising options for cutting emissions and demonstrates that agriculture and land use changes offer at least as many opportunities for mitigating climate change as the energy sector.

Sachs (2015:484) states that the goals address a challenge that has been more than forty years in public awareness and twenty years in international law but has not successfully been addressed. Monkelbaan (2019:5) highlights that the SDGs provide an opportunity for all stakeholders to establish commitments and express their preferences and interests on the broad issues they discuss.

SDGs are a multi stakeholder process which requires hands-on effort and engagement across the public sector, the private sector, civil society, governments, individuals, academia, and research centers (Sachs, 2015:495). Private companies can take the lead in building and operating large-scale green energy systems (Sachs, 2015:499). Everyone must be involved in the implementation to guarantee success.

Other crucial sustainability challenges that are covered by the SDGs, include poverty and inequality, hunger, loss of biodiversity, habitat destruction, waste, depletion of fish stocks, air and water pollution, topsoil erosion, deforestation and desertification, rising food prices, resource and water scarcity, socio-economic imbalances, public health challenges, conflict, decreasing social trust and social capital, and institutional failure (Monkelbaan, 2019:8). While these are all important the study focuses on the climate change challenge as to assess the reason why it is not discussed much by the

agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare, and whether these firms have adopted it in their operations.

2.5 Zimbabwe climate change response strategy

According to Brazier (2017:92), the Government of Zimbabwe is committed to addressing climate change challenges based on its Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDCs) which demonstrates the country's adaptation actions with mitigation co-benefits to address GHG emissions. Furthermore, Brazier (2017:90) states that the country subscribes to the principle of common but differentiated responsibilities in line with national capabilities enshrined in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

According to Brazier (2017:92) Zimbabwe's national climate change governance processes derive their authority from the Constitution of Zimbabwe, the National Climate Change Response Strategy (NCCRS), the National Climate Policy (NCP) and the laws, Acts and statutory instruments that give effect to the commitments under the conventions, treaties and protocols to which Zimbabwe is a signatory. In addition to being party to the UNFCCC, Kyoto Protocol, Montreal Protocol and The UN Convention to Combat Desertification, Zimbabwe has facilitated the creation of an enabling environment, policies and partnerships with development partners. The NCCRS, the NCP and the Climate Change Management Department in the Ministry of Environment Water and Climate, which coordinates climate change matters, including finance, are part of this (Brazier, 2017:93).

The vision of the NCP is a climate-resilient and a Zimbabwe with low CO₂. The aim is to climate proof all socio-economic development sectors to reduce Zimbabwe's vulnerability to climate related disasters, while implementing a low emission development pathway. The purpose of the policy is to guide climate change management, enhance national adaptive capacity, scale up mitigation actions, facilitate domestication of global policies and ensure compliance with global mechanisms.

The Zimbabwe's National Climate Change response strategy promotes the implementation of activities to reduce the amounts of GHGs emitted and to promote a green economy (Brazier, 2017:93). Assessment and control measures are stipulated to tackle the challenge of climate pollutants, as well as a strategy to promote cleaner technologies as a mitigation measure.

Zimbabwe's GHGs mitigation pledge to the UNFCCC for the period 2020 to 2030 of CO₂, CH₄ and NO₂ from the energy sector was given as 33% below the projected business as usual energy emissions per capita (Brazier, 2017:93). Some of the projects listed by the government to achieve this goal are solar water heater projects, energy efficiency improvement, Integrated Waste Management, reviewing the transport system and Sustainable energy alternatives of curing tobacco.

The National Code on Corporate Governance Zimbabwe (2015), the Public Entities Corporate Governance Act (10:31), and S.I.134 of 2019 Securities and Exchange have made provisions for using the Global Reporting Initiatives (GRI) standards for corporate sustainability in their rules (Ndamba 2021). Companies are required to apply the GRI sustainability reporting Standards, which focuses on the economic, environmental and social impacts of the activities of a company, and hence its contributions towards sustainable development. The Public Entities Corporate Governance Act (Chapter 10:31) requires public sector entities to manage and account for their ESG impacts and opportunities (Ndamba, 2021). As a result, some public companies have been producing publicly available sustainability reports.

The Zimbabwe Government developed the long-term Low Emission Development Strategy (LEDS), for the period 2020 to 2050, in response to the global climate change crisis, which sets the course for reducing emissions, while ensuring sustainable economic development for the country (Zimbabwe Progress Review Report of SDGs, 2020:110). The aim is to reduce GHG emissions or increase CO₂ sequestration in forests and soils while contributing to socioeconomic development. It outlines mitigation measures which seek to reduce the costs of electricity, agricultural production, and fuel consumption.

However, Dhlakama *et al.* (2019:18) cite the AfDB (2011:2) which states that Zimbabwe's GHG emissions constitute only approximately 0.062% of the global total while Africa as a whole contributes less than 7%. The GoZ (2012) cited by Dhlakama *et al.* (2019:18) states that the major sources of GHG emissions in Zimbabwe are energy (49%); agriculture (40%); waste (6%) and industry (5%). According to Zimbabwe's Third National Communication to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) whose reporting year was 2006, the country's estimated emissions were 22,019 GgCO₂ eq (Giga tonnes of CO₂ equivalent) while emission removals from the atmosphere through Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector were estimated at 83,000 GgCO₂ eq making Zimbabwe a net carbon sink GoZ (2016:21).

Since the UNFCCC and subsequent protocols, developing countries and small islands have come to the realisation that in their own case adaptation is more urgent than mitigation (Dhlakama *et al.*, 2019:4). As a result Zimbabwe's climate change policy, and any legal instruments, show a prioritisation of adaptation even though there is recognition of the need for mitigation.

2.6 The manufacturing industry's contribution to climate change

Industry's GHG sources are either direct or indirect. Direct GHG emissions come from sources that an industry owns or controls, while indirect GHG emissions come from sources where the point of release is not within the company, but either upstream or downstream in the supply chain (Kolk & Pinkse, 2009:69). Kolk and Pinkse (2009:69) cite (Phillips, 2004) who points out that some of the industry owned sources of GHG are emissions from fossil fuel combustion for electricity, heat or steam generation, production processes for manufacture, transportation and fugitive emissions, such as refrigerants and methane. Large scale commercial agriculture and forest clearing also contribute to greenhouse gas emissions (Brazier, 2017:7). As industry grows more of these emissions are released.

Historically, agricultural productivity became a prerequisite for the expansion of manufacturing because it released members of a rising population to engage in human

activities other than hunting and gathering food (Penna, 2015:164). With agriculture came early settlements, towns, and eventually cities, where a growing number of manufactured goods became apparent.

The energy sector is the dominant source of GHG emissions. Chen *et al.* (2017:8) cite Quadrelli and Peterson (2007) who illustrated that the share of greenhouse gas emissions from various sectors comprises of 84% energy sector, 8% agriculture, 5.5% industrial processes and 2.5% waste. The agricultural manufacturing industry heavily depends on the energy sector for its operations though it is viewed as a smaller independent contributor. Agriculture and waste also constitute a big part of the industry's processes.

Waste management is important for managing the environmental impact of waste products at the end of the production process, including the GHG emissions. Taking plastics waste as an example, global production of plastics was around 288 million metric tons in 2012, but only around 10 % was recycled (Chen *et al.*, 2017:414).

Industry manufacturing processes have the potential to emit carbon dioxide and methane. According to the USEPA (2014) report on Climate, change indicators in the United States of America show that methane emissions result from livestock and agricultural practices and from the anaerobic decay of organic waste in municipal solid waste landfills (Chen *et al.*, 2017:54). Other gases emitted from a variety of industrial processes include nitrous oxide and fluorinated gases.

Penna (2015:163) points out that manufacturing produces a considerable quantity of goods for large a population to develop systematic local and regional trading networks meanwhile, the process unleashes pollutants that have local, regional, and hemispheric environmental effects. Therefore, it is important to investigate how the manufacturing industry is addressing the issues of pollution.

Deforestation has become a major problem as forests are cleared in preparation for agriculture, fencing, firewood for cooking, tobacco curing and brick making. Zimbabwe is losing its forest cover at a rate of 9% per decade, with 36% of its forests having been lost between 1990 and 2015 (Brazier, 2017:32). This was at a time when

the manufacturing industry was very productive. The tobacco industry which operates its manufacturing plants in Harare has experienced exponential growth in the last two years, with growth rate exceeding those of the last decade.

According to Mickler and Ramutsindela (2020:60) state that industry in general can be an economic driver and contributor to poverty alleviation through job creation, infrastructure development and payments to the national purse but can also have deleterious impacts by being a source of environmental disturbance, social degradation and corruption. To address this, the SDG framework offers a solution on development outcomes and measuring matrices that enable the alignment of industry and individual companies' strategy with national and local priorities (Mickler & Ramutsindela, 2020:60). Mickler and Ramutsindela (2020:60) state that the SDGs further create opportunities for partnerships to catalyse shared investments for greater benefits and strengthen the engagement with local stakeholders

Industry's impact on climate change is greater than that of the public. Vollmann (2018:154) cited Gutowski *et al.* (2013) who stated that worldwide industry uses approximately one third of all energy used globally and emits 14 billion tonnes of CO₂ and 50 mega tons of Sulfur dioxide (SO₂), almost 40% of all global anthropogenic emissions from energy and industrial processes each year. This data shows how big the impact the manufacturing industry has on the overall climate change problem.

The European Union's Emission Trading Scheme (EU ETS) established a mandatory CO₂ cap-and-trade system, which addresses emissions from major sources throughout the EU. The scheme covers about 45% of the CO₂ emissions, from more than 11,000 heavy energy-using installations in power generation and manufacturing industry (Chen *et al.*, 2017:276). The aim of the scheme is to assist Europe in achieving compliance with the Protocol's requirements, and it is a cornerstone of the EU's policy to combat climate change. Such regulation is non-existent in Zimbabwe and Africa at large.

Many companies' primary business metrics, key performance indicators and incentives focus predominantly on production, cost and profitability while neglecting

the sustainability of business through social development (Mickler & Ramutsindela, 2020:62). Mickler and Ramutsindela (2020:62) highlight that a lot of companies are now mapping existing business activities to the SDGs but the exercise stops at this level with no significant change to drive greater levels of industry contribution to the SDGs.

2.7 Climate Change Sustainable Development Goal strategies

Sovacool and Brown (2009) and Ostrom (2010) cited in Graedel and Frosch (2010:193) highlighted that successfully addressing climate change in the long run requires encouraging simultaneous actions at many scales and capitalizing on the unique benefits to be found at each different scale of action. National goals and policies must be implemented through the actions of the private sector, state, local governments, individuals and households in order to achieve the goal. The common strategies for reaching the goal are mitigation of GHG and adaptation to climate change impacts.

According to Chen *et al.* (2017:v) mitigating climate change means cutting and sequestering emissions of GHGs to prevent further increases in their atmospheric concentrations as well as reducing concentrations to levels deemed less unsafe than they were before the start of the industrial revolution. Chen *et al.* (2017:v) define adaptation as finding ways that can help reduce the impacts of climate change on society, the economy, and the environment. There is need for a balance between mitigation and adaptation to best deal with the situation.

The purpose of climate change mitigation is to enact measures to limit the extent of climate change according to Chen *et al.* (2017:10). Chen *et al.* (2017:11) further state that mitigating climate change demands creating a sustainable environment and also building a sustainable economy through renewable energy resources. It appears that the most obvious route for climate change mitigation is to move away from fossil fuel energy sources and to eliminate consumption of petrochemical products. However, both drastic measures are costly and would demand readjusting the lifestyles of modern society and the growing population.

Technological climate change mitigation solutions include methods for reducing the amount of GHGs entering the atmosphere, facilitating the removal of GHGs from the atmosphere and manipulating the earth's natural systems in order to reduce the impacts on climate change, which is known as geo-engineering (Brazier, 2017:150). The removal of GHGs from the atmosphere is commonly referred to as carbon sequestration, and there are several methods that have been specified by scientists of doing this.

Ideally adaptation strategies are implemented in anticipation of climate change so that people, animals, economic sectors and natural systems are prepared and protected from possible disruptions Chen *et al.* (2017:12). Adaptation in general calls for a change or adjustment in the way of doing things. That means businesses that adapt to the climate change SDG will need to make changes to the traditional ways of business operations.

Most adaptation measures are not specifically related to climate change but are essentially sustainable ways to improve the management of resources and communities (Brazier, 2017:107). These measures can lower GHG emissions or help to draw greenhouse gases from the atmosphere. Brazier (2017:107) states that planting trees and safeguarding forests will protect the soil and improve the ability of rainfall to recharge underground water stores, and the trees will help to sequester CO₂ from the atmosphere, thus reducing global warming.

The type of industry and structure of the industry play a role in the process of developing a competitive climate change strategy (Kolk *et al.*, 2009:96). The industry dynamics, which companies adopt in the interaction with their competitors, also affects their behaviour regarding climate change. Thus climate change adoption can be used as a competitive advantage as consumers are becoming more environmentally conscious and want to be associated with environmentally friendly companies and products. As a result, the increased consumer awareness of climate change may create the opportunity for agriculture manufacturing businesses to service global markets with climate-friendly products.

Top management's commitment to climate change strategies, organisational structure and the organisational culture play a crucial role in the company's adoption levels (Kolk *et al.*, 2009:96). In some cases climate change is viewed as any other business issue, which has to compete with other investment opportunities, while in other instances climate related activities are pursued as a moral obligation but not necessarily to make a profit (Kolk *et al.*, 2009:98). It is, therefore, critical for organisations to make their climate change decisions from an informed position.

Griggs *et al.* (2021:133) suggest that carbon pricing through a carbon tax or cap-and-trade market mechanism is useful for reducing carbon intensity in industrial processes and provide governments with funds to help innovation and compliance in the industrial sector. This involves the government placing a limit, on emissions from carbon-intensive industries and firms to obtaining permits, that can be bought and sold, thus placing a price on carbon which will encourage companies to reduce their carbon emissions to avoid paying the cost for carbon allowances (Buffa, Scholl & Zabin, 2009:5). Large energy users and large emitters of GHG, will face higher costs from the implementation of such policies (Buffa *et al.*, 2009:11).

Industry will either upgrade their facilities to make them more energy efficient or buy carbon allowances that permit them to continue emitting. If companies pass on the costs to consumers, the consumers will change their consumption behaviour in response to the price increase, thus reducing the demand for carbon-intensive products consumed and ultimately energy used. However, there is an argument against the imposition of these costly measures to industry, which can result in firms closing down operations due to the economic impact on their businesses.

According to Kolk and Pinkse (2009:91), the generally accepted initial activities in a company's response to climate change are emissions measurement, target setting and reporting, then evaluating and implementing options for the reduction of GHG emissions in order to reach the aspirations expressed by the climate change targets. Usually all that is required is activities that involves some behavioral and technological changes.

Some examples of behavioral changes indicated by Kolk and Pinkse (2009:91) who cite Okereke (2007) comprise improving employee awareness of the implications of their use of office equipment such as printers and computers on a company's energy consumption or reducing the carbon impact of business travel. Options for technological changes include measures to improve energy efficiency and reduce energy consumption such as improving insulation of company properties, introducing energy management systems aimed at a better management of lighting and heating of buildings, and replacing outdated, energy-inefficient production installations (Kolk & Pinkse, 2009:91).

According to Brazier (2017:150), finding alternative energy sources is one of the major ways that the world can fight climate change. This includes energy sources such as solar energy or wind energy.

Companies have a choice between pursuing product or process oriented improvements and emissions trading, or do both (Kolk & Pinkse, 2009:91). Emissions trading schemes play a key role in climate policy, which opens up ways to comply with the regulatory or voluntary targets set for emissions reduction Kolk and Pinkse (2009:99). Furthermore, companies that can reduce emissions at a relatively low cost can sell the ensuing surplus of emissions credits at a profit to other companies. Kolk and Pinkse (2009:102) state that emissions trading has emerged as the main policy instrument to combat climate change.

Life cycle assessments of GHG help to guide decision making about the best climate change mitigation strategy and avoid intuitive decisions. Life cycle assessments of GHG emissions are measures that were developed for analyzing products from resource extraction to waste disposal, and are usually part of wider environmental assessments, which also cover other environmental impacts (Chen *et al.* 2017:62). They include initiatives such as decreasing the household energy consumption of the products and running program to increase consumer awareness in order to help customers reduce emissions.

Some of the companies that do not consider emissions from the use of products or services by their consumers argue that the use of products and services does not lead

to any significant emissions (Kolk & Pinkse, 2009:101). More often than not these companies point their fingers at other entities as the GHG emitters and fail to realise their own implications.

Supply chain measures for compensation is a strategy employed to avoid the need for emissions cuts within a company (Kolk & Pinkse, 2009:103). In this instance, the company looks for solutions to ensure that activities and sources of high emissions are carried out somewhere else in the supply chain or that emissions are reduced further up the supply chain. The most common supply chain measure is monitoring the carbon intensity of suppliers or the supplied raw materials. Companies would have to request disclosure of carbon emissions measurement of each and every supplier they engage. However, the challenge is that some companies will resort to reducing internal emissions by subcontracting or outsourcing certain high-emissions activities such as transportation and distribution to reduce their own internal emissions while increasing those of business partners.

Another supply change measure strategy is to replace inputs with a high potential for GHG emissions with those with lower emissions, such as substituting fossil fuels with carbon free renewable energy sources (Kolk & Pinkse, 2009:103). Within the context of the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare this means using energy generated from green energy sources such as solar and hydroelectricity.

Waste management and recycling are important considerations of resource sustainability and GHG emissions. The management of waste is important for controlling the environmental impact of organic chemical products at the end of their life (Chen *et al.*, 2017:414). Wrap (2010) cited in Chen *et al.* (2017:414) states that recycling can reduce the energy demand, and therefore the GHG emissions, of plastic manufacture by about 0.6t of CO₂ equivalent per ton of plastic recycled compared to land filing. Therefore, maximizing recycling is a vital tool in the pursuit of sustainability in the manufacturing industry from economic, social, and environmental perspectives.

Effective information and communication processes that allow people, especially those who are the most marginalised, to be their own agents of change are

prerequisites for sustainable development and the success of the SDGs (British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) World Service Trust 2010) cited in Mickler and Ramutsindela (2020:72). Mickler and Ramutsindela (2020:74) further state that to adequately adapt and mitigate the effects of climate change, both the countries and citizens in Africa need to have sufficient knowledge and understanding on climate change.

African citizens are at humanity's climate change frontline, but they are also among the least informed about human induced global climate change, its causes and its consequences (Mickler & Ramutsindela 2020:74). The report by the BBC further states that broader public understanding of a range of climate change issues is required if Africa is to adequately respond and adapt to climate change (BBC World Service Trust Report, 2010).

Shanahan 2009 cited in Mickler and Ramutsindela (2020:74) state that the quantity of climate change coverage in African media is disproportionate to the level of threat it poses to the continent. Industry can, therefore, play a crucial part in attempting to close this gap by building awareness in their own media campaigns and interactions with the communities in which they operate. Sustained efforts from industry and other stakeholders, which includes consistent dialogue and a two-way flow of information will empower African citizens to adequately address, adapt and mitigate the dangers and threats of climate change.

2.8 Conclusion

Global warming is real and it is one of the most urgent problems that human nature has been faced with. The causes of climate change and the solutions to the climate change related problem are a contestable subject in the business sector, and inevitably in the manufacturing industry. The starting point is to build awareness of the crisis and the many plausible solutions in all stakeholders. The next step is for everyone to play their part no matter how small or seemingly insignificant.

The next chapter will cover the chosen research philosophy and draw a comparison with alternative philosophies, while justifying the relevance of the chosen philosophy. An outline of the research strategies including the research methodologies will be given. Next research instruments that have been utilised to achieve the goal will be justified. The research design, target population, sample design, data collection methods, and data analysis methods of the study will be discussed and reasons for choosing the design will be given.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the research philosophy chosen for the study to address the research problem outlined in Chapter One, in relation to other philosophies. This includes the research paradigm, research approach and research method which were employed. The chapter will detail the required type of data, the data collection instrument and the strategies used to analyse the data, including the reasons for selecting the methods and strategies used.

3.2 Research Design

According to Memon, Qureshi, and Syed (2016:17), research design is the plan and the procedures for research that stretches the decisions from general assumptions to detailed methods of data collection and analysis. Creswell (2014:41) defines research design as types of inquiry in qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches that provide specific direction for procedures. While Leavy (2017:vii) sees research design as building a structure or plan for research, using qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods as the structure using considerations such as the topic and purpose. The above definitions all concur that research design provides the framework and processes for planning a thorough and thoughtful study.

The type of research design chosen depends on the nature of the research problem, the aim and the objectives of the intended research. The research design is selected based on whether the study is using the quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods study. Quantitative studies apply a quantitative design such as the causal-comparative research and correlational research. Qualitative studies on the other hand apply qualitative designs such as explanatory, descriptive and exploratory research.

The most commonly used research designs are exploratory, experimental and descriptive among others which are summarized in the discussion that follows.

3.2.1 Exploratory design

Exploratory studies are useful where not much is known about the subject being studied. They often require informal setups such as interviews and discussion groups. The answers derived from the study are not sufficient for decision making but simply provide a better understanding of the subject under study. Case studies involve the analysis of one or more sites over a certain period of time. Case studies are conducted in their natural setting to gather information on the site.

An exploratory study using qualitative methods was chosen because not much has been written about the adoption of the climate change SDG by the manufacturing industry in Harare. The chosen research methodology comprised semi-structured interviews, supported by primary and secondary sources such as reports, policy and legal documents from the companies and industry associations involved, and from various climate change bodies.

3.2.2 Explanatory design

Explanatory research aims to explain the relationship among variables and to identify how the components of a phenomenon are connected. Lewis, Saunders and Thornhill (2016:175) describe explanatory research as studies that establish causal relationships between variables. The emphasis is to study a situation or a problem in order to explain the relationships between the concerned variables. An explanatory study is likely to use a deductive approach, using theoretical propositions to test their applicability in the study, in order to build and verify an explanation (Lewis, Saunders & Thornhill, 2016:185).

3.2.3 Descriptive Design

Descriptive research design seeks to gain an accurate profile of events, persons or situations (Lewis *et al.*, 2016:175). Lewis *et al.* (2016:175) emphasise that it is important to have a clear picture of the phenomenon on which the data was collected prior to the collection of the data. The data collected needs to be described and meaningful conclusions must be drawn from the described data.

3.2.4 Causal-comparative Design

Causal-comparative research design, which uses experimental design takes place within a carefully designed, controlled environment and usually involves special treatments of different groups that will then be compared to reach a conclusion. Experiments are either conducted in the laboratory or in the field to test and analyse different variables. Surveys involve the gathering of data about views, situations or behaviour using questionnaires or interviews (Creswell, 2014:41). Data analytical techniques are then used to draw meaning from the data. In a correlational design, the investigators use the correlational statistic to describe and measure the degree or relationship between two or more variables or sets of scores (Creswell, 2014:41). Causal design is when the investigator compares two or more groups in terms of a cause, or an independent variable to study something that has already happened.

3.2.5 Correlational Design

Correlational research design is used in experimental studies to establish the relationship between variables (Bridgmon and Martin, 2012:66). Creswell (2009:59) states that the variables are related to answer a research question or make predictions about what the researcher expects or predicts the results will show. Sometimes when predictions are tested over and over again new theories are formed.

The study followed an exploratory research design due to the complex and sensitive nature of the subject, the small number of companies involved, and the exploratory nature of the research influenced. Additionally, there is little or unknown research that has been carried out on the effective adoption of the climate change SDG by the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare, and Zimbabwe at large. The chosen methodology is ideal for investigating an area or issue on which little previous work has been carried out and was helpful for unveiling patterns and hypotheses around the adoption of the climate change SDG. The methodology justifies the reasons why the patterns and links occur in the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare.

The researcher sought to listen to participants and build an understanding based on what was said by the participants. Interviews were conducted with Safety, Health, Environment and Quality (SHEQ) Managers at 7 different agriculture manufacturing

companies using interviews with open ended questions were used. Additional document data from the companies' environmental management policies were studied. The study analysed themes and patterns and to make interpretations. All the data gathered is presented in a qualitative format.

3.3 Research Philosophy

There are two approaches to gathering and reporting information in research, namely qualitative and quantitative. Creswell (2014) defines qualitative research as a means for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem through a process of emerging questions, data collected in the participants' settings, inductively analysing the data, then making interpretations of the meaning of the data. Creswell (2014) further defines quantitative research as the means for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables.

Qualitative research deals with phenomena that are difficult or impossible to quantify mathematically, such as beliefs, meanings, and attributes Lewis *et al.* (2016:165). Qualitative research is important where the aim is to discover the underlying motives of human behaviour. Through such research we can analyse the various factors which motivate people to behave in a particular manner or which make people like or dislike a particular thing.

The investigation into the adoption of the Climate Change Sustainable Development Goal by the manufacturing industry in Harare cannot be quantified. It required the analysis and interpretation of the meaning of the behaviour of the organisations under study. Hence, the investigation was done using a qualitative or phenomenological approach. The focus was on understanding a phenomenon about the adoption of the climate change SDG by the manufacturing industry from the perspective of the participants and then using that to make conclusions.

3.4 Research Strategy

The two strategies of enquiry using positivist research strategies also known as quantitative research and phenomenological research strategies also referred to as qualitative research. These research methods in these strategies are listed below.

Positivist Research Strategy

- Surveys

Phenomenological research strategies

- Interviews
- Ethnography
- Case Study
- Grounded theory
- Narrative research

Explanations of each of these methods are given below.

3.4.1 Positivist Research Strategy

3.4.1.1 Surveys

Creswell (2014) stated that: "...survey research provides a quantitative or numeric description of trends, attitudes, or opinions of a population by studying a sample of that population". The survey strategy is mostly used to answer questions that address 'what', 'who', 'where', 'how much' and 'how many' of the subject being studied.

3.4.2 Phenomenological research strategies

The main phenomenological research strategies are interviews, ethnography, case study, grounded theory, narrative research, and phenomenological research.

Phenomenological research is where the researcher identifies the essence of human experiences about a phenomenon as described by participants (Creswell, 2014). It involves studying a small number of participants through extensive and prolonged engagement to develop patterns and relationships of meaning.

According to Creswell (2014), experimental research seeks to determine if a specific treatment influences an outcome. The purpose of the experiment is to study the probability of a change in an independent variable causing a change in another dependent variable.

3.4.2.1 Interviews

Lewis *et al.* (2016:388) define research interviews as a purpose driven conversation between two or more people, requiring the interviewer to establish rapport and ask concise and unambiguous questions, which the interviewee willingly listens to attentively and responds. Interviews of participants in the research can be structured or unstructured. The interviews often use open ended questions with the aim of probing the participant to share in-depth data.

3.4.2.2 Ethnography

Ethnography is a written account of a group of people which is used to study the culture of the group (Lewis *et al.*, 2016:87). It is useful for studying social and cultural problems in a specific group.

3.4.2.3 Case study

A case study is an in-depth inquiry into a topic or phenomenon within its real-life setting, with the aim of understanding the dynamics of the topic being studied (Lewis *et al.*, 2016:184). This approach leads to the development of rich in-depth descriptions and theories of the subject.

3.4.2.4 Grounded theory

Creswell (2014) defines grounded theory as an enquiry strategy in which the researcher derives a general, abstract theory of a process, action, or interaction grounded in the views of participants. It involves the frequent comparison of data with emerging categories and theoretical sampling of different groups to maximize the similarities and the differences of information.

3.4.2.5 Narrative research

In narrative research, the researcher studies the lives of individuals and asks one or more individuals to provide stories about their lives which are retold by the researcher into a narrative chronology.

The study used interviews as a phenomenological strategy. This helped to uncover meaning of adopting the climate change SDG goal by individual manufacturing companies in Harare. Using the lens of key environment managers in selected companies, the focus was on how each company views their contribution of the achievement of this goal and the measures the company is putting in place to contribute to its success.

3.5 Target population

The targeted population was all environmental management practitioners based at agriculture manufacturing companies in Harare.

Due to the population being small and difficult to involve in the study a sample of randomly selected managers who were available to participate in the study was selected.

3.5.1 Sampling

Sampling is the process through which a researcher selects several individual cases from a larger population (Leavy, 2017:76). It is a process of selecting a specified number of individuals from the key population of potential participants of a study.

The reasons for sampling are that it is cheaper than conducting an analysis of the entire group under study, and it provides the needed information quicker. Lewis *et al.* (2016:272) explain that sampling enables the researcher to reduce the amount of data necessary to collect by considering only data from a subgroup rather than all possible cases.

Lewis *et al.* (2016:273) cite Becker (1998) who stresses the importance of ensuring the selected sample represents the full set of cases in a way that is meaningful, and which can be justified.

Clark and Creswell (2018:269) explain that the sampling procedure involves determining the participants who will provide data in the study, how the participants will be selected, the location for the research, and the number of participants needed to answer the research questions. In a qualitative study, the researcher selects a small number of participants who have experienced the central phenomenon being explored in the study and can provide in depth information about the central phenomenon, while in quantitative research, the researcher uses sampling procedures to select a larger number of individuals who represent a segment of the population (Clark & Creswell, 2018:269).

The sample size for this qualitative research is 7. The haphazard sampling methodology in the form of convenience sampling was chosen as a result of the time constraints, limited number of willing participants and to manage the costs of carrying out the study.

3.5.2 Kinds of sampling

The two broad categories under sampling methodologies are probability and non-probability sampling. These are discussed in the following paragraphs.

3.5.2.1 Probability sampling

In probability sampling, every member of the target population has a known chance of being included in the sample. According to Leavy (2017:78), probability sampling involves the use of strategy in which samples are selected such that every member in the population has a known and non-zero chance of being selected. This means each member has the same chance of being included.

The different types of sampling under probability sampling are Simple random, Systematic, Stratified and Cluster. These are explained as follows:

a) Simple random

In simple random sampling, every member in the study population has an equal chance of being selected Leavy (2017:79).

b) Systematic

Systematic sampling involves selecting the sample at regular intervals from the sampling frame (Lewis *et al.*, 2016:289). This requires numbering each member in the study population, calculating the sampling fraction, randomly selecting the first member, then selecting subsequent members systematically using the sampling fraction to determine the frequency of selection.

c) Stratified

Stratified sampling is where the target population is divided into two or more relevant and significant strata based on one or more attributes. A random sample is then drawn for each of the strata (Lewis *et al.*, 2016:296).

d) Cluster

In cluster sampling, the researcher first identifies intact groups or clusters of members, such as businesses, then randomly selects groups and studies the members within those groups (Clark & Creswell, 2018:270). In some cases, all members in a cluster are selected as part of the sample.

3.5.2.2 Non-probability sampling

Non-probability sampling involves selecting members who are available and can be studied (Clark & Creswell, 2018:270). The participants are randomly selected; thus members do not have a definite chance of being selected. Examples of non-probability sampling types include convenience sampling and snowball sampling.

a) Convenience sampling

Convenience sampling involves selecting members haphazardly because they are easily available or most convenient to obtain for the sample (Lewis *et. al.*, 2016:304).

b) Snowball sampling

Snowball sampling is a sampling strategy in which one case organically leads to another (Leavy, 2017:80). In other words, the participants of the research refer other individuals to also participate.

The sampling methodology of this study was convenience and non-probability as required for phenomenological research philosophy. The agricultural manufacturing businesses selected were diverse, therefore, they represent all typical cases, and also offer appropriate illustrative scenarios providing justification regarding the purpose of the research.

A snowball sampling approach was also used to get participants referrals from the initially recruited participants because it was difficult to find the required number of participants. The researcher asked participants to refer other individuals who would be willing and able to participate.

3.6 The Research Instrument

Research instruments are tools used for collecting data for the study. The most common research instruments are interviews and questionnaires (Creswell 2014:45). Other instruments are observation and examination of secondary sources. A semi-structured open-ended questionnaire was used to collect data from interviewed participants.

“A research interview is a purposeful conversation between two or more people, requiring the interviewer to establish rapport and ask concise and unambiguous questions, to which the interviewee is willing to respond, and to listen attentively”

(Lewis *et al.*, 2016:388). Interviews are conducted using open-ended questions and qualitative observations and require skills in analyzing qualitative text data, including coding text and developing themes and descriptions based on codes used to analyse the data. Interviews help to further explore answers by asking additional questions.

Interviews are categorised as either structured interviews, semi-structured interviews or unstructured or in-depth interviews. Structured interviews use questionnaires based on a predetermined and identical set of questions, while in semi-structured interviews the researcher has a list of themes and possibly some key questions to be covered, although their use may vary from interview to interview (Lewis *et al.*, 2016:391). On the other hand, unstructured or in-depth interviews are informal with no predetermined list of questions to ask, according to Lewis *et al.* (2016:391). Though informal, uninstructed interviews follow a pattern of an agreed meeting place and time.

Lewis *et al.* (2016:437) describe questionnaires as data collection methods in which each person is asked to respond to the same set of questions in a predetermined order. It includes face to face and telephone questions as well as those answered in the absence of the interviewer. Questionnaires provide an efficient way of collecting responses from a large sample for a quantitative analysis.

Observation involves the systematic viewing, recording, description, analysis and interpretation of people's behaviour (Lewis *et al.*, 2016:354). This instrument is useful for research questions and objectives that are concerned with what people do because watching them do it is an obvious way in which to discover their objectives.

Secondary sources refer to documents used for research which were originally created for a different purpose (Lewis *et al.*, 2016:437). It is important to consider the validity and applicability of the secondary source to the research question. A semi-structured interview approach was used to conduct an exploratory discussion which allowed the researcher to explore and understand the internal dynamics of the research topic. The research questions were used to draw a list of open-ended questions which the participants were asked during the interviews. The researcher asked the questions in person and in some instances over a telephone call, wrote down the responses and

made notes of the behaviours of the participants. An audio recording device was used with the consent of the participants to enable accurate analysis of data after the interview.

3.6.1 Questionnaire construction

The interview included questions in the areas of the SHE Offers' understanding of climate change and the SDGs; views about the SDGs; what they think should be done to mitigate climate change; steps their organisation are taking to mitigate climate change; the factors of implementing the climate change SDG by businesses; and the strategies that can improve the adoption of the climate change SDG.

According to Lewis *et al.* (2016:408) open-ended questions are designed to encourage the interviewee to provide an extensive and developmental answer and are useful for obtaining facts.

3.6.2 Interviews

The interview methods available to qualitative researchers include in-depth, Semi-structured, oral history or life history, biographic minimalist, and focus groups (Leavy, 2017:139). According to Leavy (2017:139), semi-structured interviews are inductive or open-ended, comprising of questions that do not have a predetermined set of acceptable responses, such as true or false. Participants are able to use their own language, provide long and detailed responses, and respond to the questions in any direction they choose.

As an interview guide a list of open-ended questions was drawn to ensure all the key themes for the study were covered. Open-ended questions allow interviewees to use ideas in their own way making it possible to probe the meanings such that richer and deep data was obtained. More importantly, the discussions were led into areas that the researcher had not previously considered but which were significant for understanding and helped to address the research questions and objectives better.

Due to the semi-structured nature of the interviews the questions were not asked in a specific order but rather participants were allowed to go in different directions and the

questions asked went with their flow. Some of the questions did not have to be asked as participants had already covered the subject in their response to previous questions. Probes were used to collect richer data. The questions asked varied, but all the themes were covered in the different interviews. In some interviews, additional questions were asked to explore the research question and objectives given the nature of events the participant described.

Face-to-face interviews were conducted where possible to build rapport, pick up on visual cues, and use gestures in the data collection. Interviews were also conducted via video conferencing, telephone and email. Although not identical to face-to-face experiences, video-conferencing have many of the benefits of face-to-face interviews (Leavy, 2017:142).

A cellphone with voice-recording capacity was used to audio-record face-to-face interviews with willing participants while adhering to covid protocols of wearing masks and maintaining a distance of at least 1.5 meters. In the case of video conferencing, an online audio recorder was used to record the interviews, also only with the consent of the interviewee. The online audio recorder made it easy to share the audio recording with the interviewee who received a link to the recording. The recordings allowed the researcher to type up verbatim transcripts of interviews, which serve as part of the data.

3.7 Pilot Study

A pilot study is a practical test of the research idea, data collection instruments, interview schedule questions and overall research strategies (Leavy, 2017:116). The researcher was able to see if the research is going to work by trying it out on a small number of participants that represent the target participants well.

Two randomly selected Participants were targeted for the qualitative pilot study to minimise the total study costs. The first participant was interviewed face-to-face and the second participant was interviewed through Microsoft Teams audio video conferencing. Both participants of the pilot study were part of the overall study.

Very little changes were made to the study after the pilot, eliminating any possibilities of bias in the findings.

The different methods of conducting the interviews allowed the researcher to assess the effectiveness of each method and structure the procedures of conducting the interviews to suit the different mediums. Additionally, some of the questions asked to the participants had to be rephrased upon realisation that they were not getting the best responses. For example the question “What challenges are you facing in executing your environmental management role in your company?” was changed to “What challenges do agriculture manufacturing businesses face in implementing the climate change SDG?” because the piloted Participants were not comfortable to respond to the question for fear of being implicated as exposing their employer.

Another question that was modified to encourage participation was “What is your organisation doing to mitigate climate change?” which was rephrased as “What are agriculture manufacturing organisations doing to mitigate climate change?” Though these questions were not specifically asking about the organisations where the SHE Officers are employed, they allowed the Participants to talk about other organisations and also about their own organisations.

3.8 Conduct of Interviews

Since this study was conducted using a semi-structure qualitative approach, no questionnaires were issued to participants. A schedule of open-ended interview questions derived from themes drawn out of the research questions were used. The interviews were carried out for between 30 and 35 minutes and all data was collected instantly in the form of audio recordings. The participants were informed that the interviewer had a schedule of questions to guide the discussion.

The questions were asked in different order based on the direction the discussion took, and were sometimes rephrased to suit the interviewee, the situations being discussed and also taking into consideration previous responses. In some instances, some questions were not asked as the interviewee had already answered them indirectly. In

other instances, new questions emerged as the interviewee brought up a new idea or perspective that the researcher had not anticipated. The initial questions did not include a question about the role of the regulatory authority but the matter was a recurring issue from the first four Participants and therefore, the fifth Participant who had not brought up this issue was asked "What is the role of the regulatory authority in ensuring the adoption of the climate change SDG?"

The questions were asked to one participant at a time either face-to-face, through telephone conversations or through video conferencing. Only one interview was conducted per day to allow for preparation and transcription as well as to accommodate the interviewer and participant's work commitments. The researcher then transcribed the entire discussion for review and analysis of the qualitative data.

The chosen approach was ideal for accessing busy participants during their working hours. Telephone interviews allowed the interviews to be conducted in a timely and cost effective manner. Due to the prevailing trend of remote working, the interviewees who participated in video conferencing and telephone interviews were confident to participate in the discussion and engage in deep conversation.

The use of the telephone and voice only conferencing also facilitated participation, by allowing participants to choose a suitable time of day to be interviewed. Participants were able to pause an interview in progress when this became unavoidable.

3.9 Data Analysis

The first step in the data analysis was transcribing the audio recordings of the interviews verbatim. The next step was to ensure the transcriptions were accurate by correcting errors. The researcher repeatedly re-read transcripts and listened to audio recordings, then wrote down ideas and impressions to ensure accuracy.

A thematic analysis method was used to make meaning out of the data collected by identifying categories and themes (Lewis, 2016:579). Abbreviated letters and colours were used to code the data according to the themes and ideas which emerged. Each

theme was then given a descriptive label. An iterative and deductive approach was used to analyse the data whereby existing theory was used to shape the qualitative research process and aspects of data analysis. Since existing theory was used to formulate the research questions and objectives, the same theoretical propositions were used as a means to devise a framework to help organise and direct the data analysis.

The Analysis was an iterative process undertaken during the collection of data as well as after collection. The research propositions that the researcher commenced with at the start of the data collection exercise was tested as it was compared with the data in the study.

A thematic data analysis method was used, because it is a useful approach for qualitative research studies that involve multiple sources of data which require analysis then organising such data into themes. The analysis of data was an ongoing process which involved continually reflecting on the data, asking analytic questions, and writing memos throughout the study. The processes of data gathering and data analysis were conducted concurrently.

A phenomenological research analysis (Creswell, 2014:42) of significant statements was conducted to generate the meaning of themes in the data. The first step was for the researcher to transcribe data from the interviews and type notes from the interviews then arrange the data into respective categories dependent on the source of the data. The next step was to read through all the data and make notes on the general ideas of the participants. Next was the coding process or categorising and labeling the data into segments. Thereafter, descriptions and themes of the categories for further analysis were generated.

A narrative passage was then used to convey the findings of the analysis. Finally, an interpretation of the data was drawn. New questions that need to be asked based on the data and the analysis are included.

3.10 Validity and Reliability

Reliability refers to replication and consistency, while validity is the appropriateness of the measures used, accuracy of the analysis of the results and generalisability of the findings (Lewis, 2016:202). Lewis *et al.* (2016:205) cite Lincoln and Guba (1985) who say that all qualitative research studies should be trustworthy. Trustworthiness here, is said to be the qualitative equivalent of validity and reliability and the criteria are credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

3.10.1 Credibility

Credibility looks at ensuring that the representations of the research participants' socially constructed realities actually match what the participants intended (Lewis *et al.*, 2016:206). This was accomplished through building trust and rapport with the participants to collect sufficient data, as well as checking data, analysis and interpretations with participants. The participants were given the researcher's MANCOSA student confirmation letter to enhance the credibility of the research for study purposes. Furthermore, the participants were assured of the anonymity nature of the study findings and were given a letter written by the researcher to that effect as well as a consent form to sign. The scope to explore meanings during semi-structured interviews helped to enhance the credibility of the data collected.

3.10.2 Transferability

Transferability refers to the extent to which the findings of a research study are applicable to other settings and the aim of the study is to explore, explain and provide insights that can be used to develop theory, rather than to provide statistical generalisations (Lewis *et al.* 2016:398). The researcher provides the reader with the opportunity to judge the transferability of the study to another setting in which the reader is interested to research by providing a full description of the research questions, design, context, findings and interpretations. The study was conducted with participants from different organisations as opposed to participants from one or two organisations and therefore produced valuable findings.

3.10.3 Dependability

Dependability in qualitative studies means recording all of the changes to produce a reliable account of the emerging research focus that may be understood and evaluated by others (Lewis *et al.* 2016:206). The researcher informed all participants that the researcher is not an expert in the subject and is seeking to learn from the participants. This helped alleviate any potential implied bias in the interviewer's line of questioning.

To avoid interviewee bias, the participants were asked to speak about the subject in general industry terms and not in relation to the organisation they work for because the study was not focused on their organisation but on the entire agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare. The issue of participation bias in terms of lack of willingness by some participants to take part in the studies was addressed by making the interviews anonymous and avoiding referring to the organisation that they work for in the data collection.

All interview participants were employed in the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare and had more than two years work experience. All participants possessed at least a Bachelor's degree in the Environmental management field thus had adequate skills and knowledge about the research topic.

3.10.4 Confirmability

Confirmability refers to the objectivity of the data. According to Lewis *et al.* (2016:243), objectivity calls for acting openly, being truthful and promoting accuracy while avoiding deception, dishonesty, partiality, reckless commitments and misrepresentation of data or findings. During the data collection stage, the researcher made sure that data was collected accurately and avoided exercising subjective selectivity in what was recorded.

The research objectivity was maintained during the analysis stage to ensure that the data collected was not misrepresented. Care was exercised to ensure that the

anonymity of individuals was maintained, by not disclosing the identity, age, name, location and employers of the participants.

3.11 Limitations of the Study

Limitations of the study are constraints placed on the ability to generalize from the results of the findings which influence the interpretation of the findings from the research (Murnan and Price, 2004). These are weaknesses that hinder the ability to generalise the results to many other situations.

In this study, there was not much literature on the actual emissions by the agriculture manufacturing industry in Zimbabwe. As a result some of the theoretical conclusions were deduced from other consumer goods manufacturing industries and the mining sector.

The research participants were generally reluctant to directly comment on the emissions of the organisations they work for and opted rather to give more detail on the environmental management initiatives that their organisations are actively carrying out. Therefore, there is need for further research to understand the real impact of agricultural manufacturing on climate change.

The majority of the interviews were conducted virtually as participants were not keen to have in person meetings due to the prevailing SARS Covid 2019 virus, which has resulted in people observing social distancing to avoid spread. This presented limitations on observation of non-verbal communication.

The small unique sample available for the study makes the extent to which the findings of the research study applicability to other settings questionable. The study is limited for use to explore, explain and provide insights that can be used to develop theory, rather than to provide statistical generalisations.

3.12 Elimination of Bias

The Oxford Dictionary definition for bias is “an inclination or prejudice for or against one person or group, especially in a way considered to be unfair.” Bias in research is the potential to influence the outcome results of the study which if not controlled can reduce the validity of the study (Clark & Creswell, 2018:298). The researcher sought to eliminate bias that can result from the personal interpretations made by the researcher of a qualitative study and the small sample size.

The selection of participants was not based on gender, ethnicity or age groups. Participants were selected based on the job position as a Safety, Health and Environment Manager within the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare.

The researcher used a reflexive approach to ensure reflection on the reason for choosing the research topic, a subjectivist ontology, an interpretivist epistemology, how to engage with the research participants, how to use the data participants and how to deal with challenges faced during the research exercise. This allowed the researcher to remain critically reflective and open to new learning.

The anonymous interviews of participants were also a means of eliminating false responses for fear of being accused of breaching the corporate non-disclosure policies. The fact that there were very few participants available in the research area also eliminated any possibilities of participant selection bias. At the same time the high response rate by approached participants reduced the risk of non-response bias ensuring the sample is representative.

3.13 Ethical Considerations

According to Lewis *et al.* (2016:239), ethics in research refer to the standards of behaviour that guide a researcher’s conduct in relation to the rights of those who become the subject of research work or are affected by the study. The aim of ethical considerations is to avoid harm to participants but rather be beneficial to the

participants, the group or organisation being researched, and the community or society within which the research occurs (Lewis *et al.*, 2016:239).

The researcher respected the rights, needs, values, and desires of the participants. The following measures were taken to protect the rights of the participants:

3.13.1 Ensuring participants have given informed consent

The research objectives were articulated verbally and in writing so that the objectives were clearly understood by the participants. This included a description of how data would be used. A letter of information was given to each of the participants explaining that participation would be entirely voluntary, and the approached participants were not obliged to take part if the participants did not wish to do so.

Each participant was informed of all data collection devices and activities. The data collection devices were limited to the interview schedule and the audio recording, which was used for willing participants, to enable the researcher to analyse the interview at a later stage.

3.13.2 Ensuring no harm comes to participants

The participants' rights, interests and requests were prioritised in reporting the data. This included honouring such requests as anonymity and the removal of any data collected, where necessary.

3.13.3 Ensuring confidentiality and anonymity

The decision regarding participant's anonymity rested with the participant. Ensuring confidentiality and anonymity means no harm will result from participating in the research.

3.13.4 Ensuring that permission is obtained

Written permission to proceed with the study was requested from the participants. Participants were provided with an Informed Consent Form to complete, which provided written proof of the participant's willingness to do so and included a statement of the participant's right to withdraw from participation at any point.

3.14 Conclusion

This chapter spelt out the type of data needed for the study, and the data collection and data analysis strategies used. A brief discussion of the chosen research philosophy in relation to other philosophies was given. The research strategy and methodologies adopted were outlined and briefly described. Finally, an introduction to the research instruments that were developed and utilised in carrying out the research is explained.

The next chapter presents the research findings, analysis of results, and an in-depth discussion of the findings. The analysis of the findings is expected to give readers insight of data that was collected, interpretation of the results as well as the implication of the topic under study and the questions the study seeks to answer.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS, DISCUSSION, AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

The impact of climate change on livelihoods are a growing concern globally. Though the major contributors to the climate change problem may be emanating from select countries and sectors of global economies the impacts are felt by all people all over the world.

The extent of the adoption of the call to action by Zimbabwe industries, and even more so the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare is unknown. Therefore, the purpose of this qualitative research was to establish the extent to which the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare has adopted the UN's call to take urgent action to reduce and prevent climate change and its impacts and to determine the factors that are inhibiting the adoption of this call to action.

An iterative deductive process was followed with information obtained from Safety Health Environment and Quality practitioners from the SMMEs in the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare. The aim of the study was to unfold the adoption of the climate change SDG by the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare.

This chapter explores and analyses the qualitative interview data which was deduced in the discussion of findings in relation to the secondary data of the literature review in chapter two with the objective of answering the research questions. The study made use of a deductive thematic analysis of the qualitative data. The thematic analysis of this data follows, starting with a brief background to the identification of the themes followed by a presentation and elaboration of the various themes that emerged.

4.2 Thematic Analysis of Qualitative Data

Sample Characteristics

All 7 participants of the research were qualified Safety, Health, Environment and Quality (SHEQ) Managers with bachelors degrees in Environmental management. 2 of the participants possessed a Master degree in the environmental management field. 6 of the participants were all employed in the Agriculture manufacturing industry, while 1 was an independent Environmental management consultant who consulted for several companies in the Agricultural manufacturing industry. All participants had more than 2 years work experience in the SHEQ field.

4.2.1 Identification of themes

With the research design aimed at evaluating the agriculture manufacturing industry's understanding of the climate change SDG and the adoption rate of the call to action by the sector in Harare, the challenge was gathering the information then analysing in a manner that would accurately address the themes identified as critical for answering the research questions.

Lewis et al (2012:579) cite Braun and Clarke (2006) who explain that thematic analysis is a foundation method for analysing qualitative data, which offers a systematic yet flexible and accessible approach to analyse qualitative data. The purpose of this approach is to search for themes, or patterns, that occur across a data set.

The process involved analysing data as the researcher collected the data and going back over earlier data and analysing to refine the way in which they are coded and categorising newly collected data then searching for analytical themes.

The iterative nature of the analysis called for the modification of the analysis as codes were revised when new data emerged, as each piece of data was analysed. The codes used were derived from the themes that had been drawn up from the onset, thus

making the coding process streamlined. This was made possible by the fact that the line of questioning in the interview was aligned to the predetermined themes.

The researcher manually colour coded all the interview transcripts and an appendix of the identified themes is provided. Data was collected from interviews that were conducted with 7 Health and Safety professionals in the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare.

A total of nine new codes emerged from the first five participants but no new codes emerged from the rest of the participants thereafter. These nine codes were used to draw the sub-themes which were further streamlined to five core themes.

Reference to available literature as well as quotes from the participants will be made to draw the links between the data collected and the themes.

4.2.2 Core Themes

The following section presents the results from the analysis. The five themes are presented:

(1) Industry awareness of climate change and the Sustainable Development Goal, (2) Zimbabwe's contribution to the climate change problem, (3) Environmental management initiatives by industry, (4) Industry challenges and problems regarding climate change mitigation action, (5) Regulatory control of climate change. The first two themes describe general awareness of the climate change SDG by both industry and the public at large. The third theme reveals the actions industry is taking that address the climate change crisis directly and indirectly and the last two themes describe the challenges that industry faces in taking urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.

The first theme reveals the understanding and appreciation of the seriousness of the climate change crisis by the key industry players in the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare. The second theme discusses the perception of how little Zimbabwe's contribution to the climate change problem is. The third theme

introduces the various environmental management initiatives that the agriculture manufacturing industry carry out that are beneficial to the environment and inevitably addressing the climate change crisis. The fourth theme outlines the challenges faced by industry which are a deterrent to taking urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts. The fifth theme explains the extent to which industry is being regulated as far as climate change control in Harare. The themes will be discussed in detail with reference to their significance to the research questions with the aim of establishing the factors that are crucial for the adoption of the climate change SDG by the Harare agriculture manufacturing industry as an indication of the relevance of the SDG to the Harare context.

4.2.3 Core Themes Analysed

4.2.3.1 Theme 1: The agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare understands and appreciates the climate change SDG

This theme emerged when the participants discussed what they understood about the SDGs. Every participant in the research was aware of the SDGs and the climate change SDG, as expected of environmental management practitioners. The participants acknowledged that climate change is a real problem and addressing it is important, as stated by Chen *et al.* (2017:12). For example Participant 1, states:

“Sustainable Development Goals all centre around issues to do with climate change as much as there are goals that talk about infrastructure, gender issues but you will see that they all try to link to climate change or they have got an interrelationship with climate change issues because what happens is because of climate change affects the girl child, affects infrastructure developments, affects education and all those issues that you find on the seventeen SDGs.”

As alluded to by Kolk *et al.* (2009:69) environmental management practitioners appreciate the fact that the actions of one company can have adverse climate related effects on many other people including in different locations, as is illustrated in the following excerpt from Participant 4:

“...with climate change ... complications, or the impacts affect everyone, even those that are actually innocent on polluting get affected.”

In all the transcripts the participants expressed belief that in the importance of the SDGs as a whole, in line with Griggs *et al.*'s (2021:19) notion that the SDGs promote human dignity and prosperity, for example Participant 2, stated:

“The SDGs themselves are quite good. They are a plan of some sort that allows whoever wants to participate to meet the goals ... in terms of managing climate change. I think the SDGs are very relevant.”

4.2.3.2 Theme 2: Zimbabwe's contribution to the climate change problem is very small at a global level but the impact experienced is significant

Referring back to the issue of low carbon emitted by developing countries and agriculture manufacturing companies, like those in Harare, discussed by Dhlakama *et al.* (2019:18), the participants made reference to how little the carbon emissions from industry in Harare are.

In this regard Participant 4 states:

“We are a very small nation. How many of our industries are fully functioning at the moment? So you can't compare our emissions to those of China ... Yes we pollute here and there but we can't compare with big houses like China and America”

Participant 1 echoed the same sentiments by stating:

“The amount of emissions into the air that we are contributing are almost insignificant.”

The same Participant went on to elaborate that:

“We are not yet industrialised. I wouldn't know the amounts of carbon emissions that we are sending in the atmosphere in terms of gigatons but it's quite insignificant...”

Industry in terms of a capacity utilization is only at about 50 to 57% so industry is slowly going up, but we have not reached a hundred percent capacity utilization, so we cannot start talking about reducing the amount of carbon sources that we are using and substituting them with costly and not very available green sources of energy sources. “

These excerpts illustrate a perception of the emissions being low and insignificant.

As a result the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare does not prioritise the climate change SDG over the other business needs. Though each company has environmental management initiatives in place, climate change mitigation is not the centre of attention in these initiatives as alluded to by Participant 6 who states:

“This issue of climate change in most organizations, is not really a topical issue. The issue that is there, the stage that we are at right now, when it comes it comes to environmental management in Zimbabwe, people are not really worried about world or global challenges that we're facing. People are worried about compliance.”

On the issue of the impact of climate change in the Zimbabwe context, the participants referred to the recurring heat waves and droughts experienced in the country as the main consequence of climate change. In that regard Participant 3 states:

“...the rainfall patterns have greatly changed from what they used to be before. I remember in October ... when I was growing up we would normally receive rains. That has changed significantly and now we start receiving the rains late November and this has to do with climate change that we are already starting to experience.”

Participant 7, in agreement with this notion states:

“Climate related disasters we are experiencing, like wildfires, droughts, floods are as a result of climate change”

Similarly, Participant 4 states:

“What the bigger nations are doing is affecting us here in the form of drought yet in Zimbabwe we do less in terms of pollution. It’s because of these bigger nations, so they need to be held responsible.”

4.2.3.3 Theme 3: The agriculture manufacturing industry implements Environmental management initiatives that address the climate change problem

By virtue of having a dedicated environmental management department headed by an expert such as a SHEQ manager, the businesses participate in a number of environmental management programs. However, it was noted that the majority of the smaller businesses did not have full time SHEQ departments and often relied on the consultancy services of SHEQ practitioners, the Operations Manager, or the Human Resources Manager to drive their environmental management initiatives. Two of the participants in the research are registered auditors who provide part time environmental audits and advisory services to small manufacturing businesses in Harare and other towns.

When asked about initiatives that organisations are doing to address the climate change SDG, the Participants gave explanations of the wide range of environmental management activities that their organisation embarks on. Brazier (2017:107) highlighted the importance of environment management practices in helping to reduce GHG emissions. With reference to experiences with businesses that he offers consulting services to, Participant 6 states:

“The issue of climate change mitigation comes as a packaged issue under Sustainability ... under the ISO where you will find that most people will be giving reference to ISO 14001.”

A common practice by all the businesses represented by the interview participants, is SHE programs that include training of employees in environmental management awareness and corporate sustainability culture. For example Participant 3 states:

“We are certified to ISO 14001 of 2015, which is an environmental management system standard. That standard entails managing the environment”

Other initiatives that Participant 3 highlighted which his organisation drives include:

- Conducting baseline surveys to do with emissions
- Measuring and monitoring emissions from the boilers and generators
- Monitoring and measuring electricity usage
- Measuring and monitoring coal usage
- Managing emissions to the public
- Monitoring and measuring water usage

Participant 4 also illustrated various initiatives that his organisation is actively carrying out that are geared towards adopting the goal as seen in the following:

“Having a SHE department or section is a step towards mitigating climate change because the company has people to help them with ideas for what to do, what to stop and where to improve”

Over and above the SHE program which includes building awareness of environmental management best practices in staff, the organisation has embarked on an innovative though quite costly process of managing waste from production.

To preserve the environment the businesses not only train their employees on environmental management practices, but they also train all visitors to their premises. In some instances, some companies go the extent of training neighbouring communities. Participant 4 states:

“For workshops like veld fire training ... we also need the neighbours to be available. We do it together so that we fight such challenges as a community.”

The interviewed participants strongly believe the initiatives they are taking to educate their staff on environmental management practices through their SHE programs will

be instrumental in creating an environmentally conscious culture. To that effect Participant 1 states:

“These programs what we normally term the SHE programs ... if the staff member has got a family, he also takes that message home. Yes, it may take time but eventually that culture is being inculcated to everyone else and it will make Zimbabwe conscious. So the message is being taken to everyone and everyone is being made aware, that we should not just throw away litter. We should not just burn our forests. We should not just waste water... If you are wasting water, you are actually wasting energy.”

The interview excerpts (primary findings) and literature citations (secondary findings) should be integrated and not presented as standalone points. i.e connecting words should be incorporated as per the example suggested in theme 1.

4.2.3.4 Theme 4: The industry is faced with notable challenges that deter climate change mitigation action

The analysis of the data received from the Participants identified a few issues that are a cause of concern when viewed against the backdrop of the urgency of the climate change crisis. The first of these is the commonly raised issue of the unavailability of financial resources to implement adequate measures of adopting climate change mitigation in industry. This factor was further broken down into lack of incentives for industry to prioritise channelling of their financial resources to climate change mitigation practices versus other pressing issues that the businesses are saddled with.

Prohibitive costs repeatedly stood out as a big challenge. To that effect Participant 6 states:

“Most of the companies in manufacturing industry have machines that consume... because they do not have money or capital injection for technological advancement.”

This response suggested that the costs of moving to cleaner technologies are too high, as illustrated in the following excerpt from Participant 1:

“The costs of green energy are more expensive than the cost of coal sourced energy so industry will still rely on that type of energy”

Participant 5 supported the cost challenges by stating:

“Addressing the climate change problem has more to do with technology and bringing the technologies on board is expensive”

When asked for his views about the climate change SDG Participant 6 states:

“Of course, it is good to shift from fossil fuels because we have learnt the negative effects of such, but for us now, to abandon these and go for solar energy may not be really sustainable for our economies and it may actually cause more harm than good.”

Participant 4 brought up an interesting perspective of how climate change effects like drought were also posing a challenge for the adoption of the climate change SDG by stating:

“When there is a drought, the companies in the agriculture manufacturing sector struggle to obtain raw materials which they use for manufacturing and have to resort to importing things like grain, which lowers their profitability.”

With lower profits the businesses have very little resources left to spend on climate change mitigation initiatives which are already costly and had not been initially budgeted for.

Other natural disasters like the COVID 19 pandemic were brought up as a deterrent by Participant 4 who states:

“When there are events like Covid-19, manufacturing plants have to close down resulting in loss of products.”

The perishable nature of agricultural manufacturing products results in losses as the raw materials and finished products cannot be stored for long periods of time. This also has a negative effect on cash flows and profitability.

Monkelbaan (2019:5) indicated that energy is the major source of carbon emissions and the solution to reducing these emissions is using alternative green energy.

Zimbabwe's main source of energy is thermal energy sourced from the Hwange thermal plant which provided 920MW energy into the national grid in 2019 with government working on expanding it to 1520MW in the following year, according to Dhlakama, Dhliwayo and Murombo (2019:114). The Power Station consumed about 2.5 million tonnes of coal per year and the small power plants in Bulawayo consume an additional 0.5million tonnes as at 2012. In comparison to other developing countries like South Africa and the developed countries like the United States, Zimbabwe's thermal power stations are relatively small (Dhlakama, Dhliwayo & Murombo 2019:115).

Some of the participants indicated that the state of the Zimbabwean economy is not good and so the country is focusing on driving economic growth first. The issue of priorities for a business poses a challenge. Participant 7 states:

“ Businesses in Zimbabwe are relying on hand to mouth, a lot of companies are actually vying towards making profits without even looking at the environmental issues.”

Participant 2 illustrates his perception of the priorities that businesses put ahead of the need to address climate change when he states:

“You know Maslow's hierarchy of basic needs, we don't have those basics yet. We are still trying to make sure that we get those basics. To then jump on to preparing for climate change is a whole huge project.”

This point was echoed by Participant 6 who states:

“It is quite difficult for developing countries like Zimbabwe to achieve because we still lack in many ways.”

Participant 5 highlighted lack of senior management commitment to the adoption of the climate change SDG in comparison to other matters the business prioritises when he states:

“Lack of top management commitment ...everyone is pushing for volumes, everyone is pushing for cost cutting, but when it comes to climate change, one from a department has to work very hard to convince top management”

Several participants mentioned that economic related challenges result in inadequate tools for measuring carbon footprint at national level. For example Participant 5 highlighted this by stating:

“We need to have a baseline and know where we are and once we know where we are in terms of our carbon footprint, we’ll then be able to set targets to then reduce that carbon footprint... As a business it is then difficult to the put in targets or mitigation measures because the information to do with our carbon footprint is missing”

4.2.3.5 Theme 5: The extent of regulatory control of climate change on the agriculture manufacturing industry is minimal

An overriding theme identified in the in-depth interviews is the minimal enforcement of regulatory control on SMMEs on climate change control. The lack of adequate regulatory control is of particular concern when considered against the fact that the World Bank (2021) released statistics indicating that the Zimbabwe economy’s recovery in 2021 was mainly due to higher agricultural production and improved capacity utilization in industry, among other factors which means the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare is growing. A growing industry that is not properly regulated will add on to the already high and undesired carbon emissions if uncontrolled.

The majority of the Participants emphasised that regulatory control on climate change mitigation was lacking. For instance Participant 2 states:

“We are not really feeling the presence of enforcement around managing climate change factors ... we need more enforcement from the relevant parties.”

This was supported by Participant 3, who states:

“The responsible authorities are not doing enough regarding the aspect of enforcement.”

Similarly Participant 4 purported:

“Our leaders, when they sit down to set these things, they come up with a very attractive, beautiful documents to read and to look at but when you get to real action being done, politics overrides everything.”

Participant 5 when asked what he recommends to maximise the adoption rate of the Climate change SDG states:

“This call for action really needs government which are a bit serious in terms of driving the agenda, in terms of the result, outside of just doing papers just for publishing purposes. Let us see things happen on the ground.”

In response to a question about what regulatory authorities were doing to enforce the adoption of the SDG Participant 6 states :

“My biggest problem is when you come up with the regulatory system it’s not only the issue of coming up with the law that matters, but also the issue of the enforcement or having the capacity to enforce that particular law because a law that is there and which is not enforced is as good as there is no law in that particular area.”

When asked what challenges the manufacturing industry faces in implementing the climate change SDG Participant 7 states:

“Our law enforcement agents sometimes get bribes. Sometimes they just leave people doing willy-nilly.”

Brazier (2017:xii) states that Zimbabwe has a National Climate Policy and a National Climate Change Response Strategy and its Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) were submitted to the UNFCCC, giving the country a clear target to work towards in terms of both adaptation to and mitigation of climate change. Additionally, the GoZ has a standalone and functional Ministry of Environment, Water and Climate responsible for water resources management, rural development, climate and environment in the country. This ministry has a Climate Change Management Department responsible for promoting best practices in climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies to enhance the country’s response and capacity to manage the impacts of climate change.

It is interesting to note that none of the interview Participants made reference to this Climate Change Management Department of the government ministry, but rather all participants made reference to the Environmental Management Authority (EMA) as the regulatory authority.

4.3 Conclusion

This chapter looked at the interpreted and discussed the data that was collected to answer the research questions. Reference was made to literature reviewed in chapter one and additional literature was discussed in the analysis. A brief explanation of the implications of the findings on the sector was given.

The next chapter will present the overall findings of the study as a whole, which are in line with the objectives and answer the research questions. This will be followed by the conclusions of the study. Lastly, some recommendations for the way forward will be made.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Findings from the Study

5.1.1 Introduction

The summary and conclusions of the study will be made in this chapter. Remarks regarding the overall adoption of the climate change SDG by the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare will follow. Recommendations of how to move forward in terms of the international best practice for prevention, mitigation and adoption of the UN climate change SDG will be made.

5.1.2 Findings from the Study

The climate change SDG calls for taking urgent action to combat climate change. The adoption of the call to take urgent action to combat climate change by the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare is pertinent for an economy that is growing. Economies are grown my industrial growth, therefore, as the agriculture industry in Harare and the country at large grows, the efforts to protect the environment and reduce GHG emissions needs to equally intensify.

5.1.2.1 Findings from the Literature Review

The SDGs were developed following the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development in 2015 as a build up to the previously adopted Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) of September 2010. The SDGs are not legally binding but they are actions derived from worldwide goals to address sustainable economic growth, peace and justice for all nations (Griggs *et al.* 2021:19). The SDGs have been instrumental in highlighting the urgency of each of the 17 goals.

Climate change is a change in the world's climate conditions as a result of the emission of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere (Brazier 2017:6). There have been debates about whether these greenhouse gas emissions are human induced and thus avoidable or if they are not an act of nature and uncontrollable Dunlap (2013:692). The general scientifically proven and accepted phenomenon is that the majority of the greenhouse gas emissions are caused by humans and so can be managed.

Scientists and environmental management experts can explain and describe the climate change phenomenon. However, it remains a difficult subject for the layman to fully comprehend.

The main cause of human induced climate change is carbon dioxide from fossil fuel and their by-products, which have been used for centuries all over the world to generate energy and other consumer goods Monkelbaan (2019:5). Industry and businesses in general are the biggest users of fossil fuels and their by-products such as plastics for operations. Inevitably, the most developed countries are the biggest users of fossil fuels due to their higher levels of industrialisation.

Zimbabwe as a member of the United Nations also signed the Paris Agreement to adopt the 17 SDGs. The GoZ's commitment to address the climate change SDG is portrayed in the various acts, laws and statutes enacted in the country, as well as active participation in the international programs and conferences. Additionally, the country crafted a local Zimbabwe's National Climate Change response strategy.

Industry's GHG emissions are both direct and indirect from fossil fuel combustion, production processes, transportation and fugitive emissions. The agricultural manufacturing industry depends on energy for operations though it is viewed as a smaller independent contributor (Kolk & Pinkse, 2009:92). Agriculture and waste which are significant emitters of GHG also comprise a big part of the industry's processes.

Industry is a bigger emitter of GHG than individuals therefore, it is more effective to monitor and control emissions at industry level than at individual levels (Chen *et al.*, 2017:8). As economies grow, as a result of growth of industry, national emissions can be reduced if industry emission levels are kept low. However, it was difficult to come across literature that showcases the extent to which the agriculture manufacturing industry is contributing to the climate change problem.

5.1.2.2 Findings from the Primary Research

This section discusses the findings from the primary research that address the objectives of the research and is broken down into sections that discuss findings for each objective.

5.1.2.2.1 The factors of implementing the Climate Change Sustainable Development Goal by the manufacturing industry in Harare

There are a number of factors of implementing the Climate change SDG by the manufacturing industry which industry can manage directly as well as those that only government and the relevant regulatory authorities can control.

In the case of businesses that have been operating prior to the introduction of the climate change mitigation phenomenon, new technologies are required to reduce the amount of carbon emission. This includes the introduction of new energy sources and other technologies that stop or reduce carbon emissions into the atmosphere. The same applies to other technologies such as those that provide green waste management, water treatment to avoid blowing down boilers after each cycle, smoke trapping from the manufacturing process and so on.

The introduction of such new technologies requires substantial capital injection to procure key resources such as solar energy sources. The lack of readily available financial resources is a major factor that inhibits the implementation of climate change mitigation strategies by the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare. Working capital constraints deter businesses from procuring new updated equipment and machinery which is designed to reduce emissions in the production process.

The issue of financial resource challenges emanates from an unfavourable economic environment. A thriving economic environment provides financial resources such as high profitability and return on investment for businesses, as well as readily available financing options such as government subsidies or incentives and financial instruments from the financial sector which industry can tap into to address the required capital injection. Poor nations like Zimbabwe cannot afford to suddenly roll

out new green energy generating plants from their own reserves at a national level, nor can they afford to offer industry incentives such as tax waivers for installing these green energy sources themselves.

The commitment of the main decision makers in an organisation who is often top management or shareholders to the adoption of climate change mitigation strategies is an important factor which affects whether the organisation acts or not. These are the people who make decisions about the allocation of resources within the organisation. In the case of the industry in Zimbabwe, there is a prevailing issue of resource constraints which often results in an issue of climate change not being a high priority. These decision makers avail the necessary resources initiative or projects proposed by the SHEQ officer to achieve the climate change mitigation goals.

Knowledge of climate change, the causes and the mitigation strategies is another important factor of implementing the climate change SDG by not only the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare. An understanding of the seriousness of climate change and the negative impact it has on livelihoods will drive people to act in every way possible to stop the crisis. When people fully comprehend danger, they naturally find ways of avoiding the danger. If they cannot save themselves, they will put pressure on those inflicting the danger or those who are able to control the perpetrators to stop the danger.

A knowledgeable and capable team of leaders in the organisation is crucial for the implementation of climate change SDG. SHEQ officers or managers are strategic leaders that can drive the implementation. These department leaders will be key in translating and executing policies and laws to the rest of the organisation. They play a key role of educating all management and staff members on the importance of the SDG. They also fulfil the crucial role of monitoring adherence to policies in the entire organisation and highlighting any anomalies. In the absence of a SHEQ manager for whatever reason, the organisation can outsource the services of a SHEQ consultant who can assist a designated leader within the organisation who can monitor the day to operations.

To some extent motivation or incentives contribute to the implementation of the climate change SDG. A good reason or benefit derived from the introduction of new ways of operating the business or spending the limited capital resources to procure new equipment and machinery can drive a business to go that route.

Regulatory control over and above the crafting of laws and regulations is an important factor in ensuring the climate change SDG is adopted. Zimbabwe has a good number of laws and policies that were enacted but industry is not being monitored for adherence. As a result, industry is implementing environmental protection measures on a voluntary basis as opposed to as a means of adhering to the rules.

5.1.2.2.2 The adoption of the Climate Change Sustainable Development Goal by the agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare

The agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare has shown commitment to managing the environment through voluntarily implementing internal environmental management programs. Though a large number of businesses do not have full time SHEQ managers nor departments, a significant number of businesses implement environmental management practices.

Smaller businesses do not address the climate change SDG directly as part of the company's focus but rather in addressing the issues of sustainability and environmental management, some initiatives combat climate change to some extent. Environmental management and sustainability practices are adopted as a means to demonstrate legal compliance.

Businesses devise internal policies aligned to national laws and policies in order to ensure compliance. The bigger companies adopt principles of sustainable development as implemented by programs such as ISO 14001. Generally, environmental management programs aim to direct the business towards sound environmental practices within the organisation. Businesses that are certified to ISO 14001 are forced to manage the environment in which they operate. This includes measuring emissions from boilers and generators, as well as measuring and monitoring the use of electricity and coal.

Organisations that adopt environmental management practices are active in raising employee awareness of environmental issues. A lot of general hands in the agricultural manufacturing industry are seasonal workers so each season when the employees are recruited for the season they go through an induction program which cover environmental management and climate change topics.

Environmental managers advocate for efficient processes within the organisations that they work for. This includes processes such as washing coal before it is put in the boiler to remove impurities that would contribute to the production of sulphur dioxide and carbon dioxide during the combustion process.

Before a new project is embarked on, an Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) which interrogate the possible impact of the inputs, outputs and processes on the environment are conducted. This means the type of new equipment and the raw materials that are being brought into industry as well as the production systems are assessed for the possibility of damage to the environment and for any potential contribution to climate change. The benefit of the EIA is that, where potential negative impacts are identified, alternatives of the proposed activity stated as part of the new project's Environmental Management Plan.

The adoption of solar powering systems has been systematic in the agriculture manufacturing industry in Zimbabwe. This is prevalent in the smaller businesses that do not require huge supplies of energy. Solar power became a popular substitute to the thermal power supplied by the Zimbabwe Energy Supply Authority (ZESA) during the periods of intense load shedding when both households and industry were forced to look for other alternatives.

Another alternative to the energy supply shortage adopted by industry is the installation of power factor correction units which ensure energy is used sparingly at maximum demand.

Though these systems are not adopted to address the climate change crisis, they do address it indirectly. In an attempt to use less energy, industry demands less coal

powered energy which means there are reduced emissions into the atmosphere which are attributable to industry.

Process efficiency is another way industry is indirectly addressing the climate change crisis. Through deliberate adequate maintenance of boilers, efficiency is realised as properly maintained and efficient boilers are able to combust 90% to 100% of the coal with minimal emissions into the atmosphere.

Organisations like the Business Council for Sustainable Development, a non-profit, are spearheading industry performance in terms of sustainability projects through conducting environmental audits. These audits include energy audits and other audits that focus on efficient processes, efficient production, efficient utilisation of raw materials, and efficient utilization of resources such as coal, water, and even on solar.

5.1.2.2.3 Strategies to improve the adoption of the Climate Change Sustainable Development Goal by the manufacturing industry in Harare

Research participants proposed various strategies to improving the adoption of the climate change SDG by, not only the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare, but by industry and the country at large. These strategies address the challenges currently facing the industry as far as adoption of the SDG.

The starting point is for GoZ to enforce laws that drive the adoption of the climate change SDG. The regulations and policies that have been crafted should be followed through by the law enforcement agents and where these are not adhered to they should be treated as crime. The same force that is used to control all other crime that is under control in the country should be applied to issues to do with combating climate change.

Over and above stringent law enforcement, business should be given incentives for implementing mitigation measures such as green energy and green waste. These incentives can come in the form of tax waivers and will motivate industry to prioritise allocating their limited financial resources towards projects that reduce carbon emissions into the atmosphere.

Increased knowledge sharing for industry practitioners not just environmental managers on the subject of climate change and industry's impact will help improve awareness. Institutions such as the Scientific and Industrial Research Development Centre (SIRDC) who already offer a lot of subsidised workshops for industry can offer training or workshops that are targeted towards building awareness of climate change as well as strategies for mitigating and adapting to climate change. These workshops can target company owners or the most senior managers of SMMEs.

The media and education system can also play a critical role in building awareness and sharing information to a larger audience. Currently awareness and commitment is predominantly limited to environmental management practitioners while the general public does not have full appreciation of the crisis and its causes. When everyone knows what climate change is and what is causing it, then more people are empowered to avoid contributing to the problem. Less people will contribute to carbon emissions and people will hold each other accountable for damaging actions. Students as young as primary school children can start being educated about the impacts of energy from fossil fuels, poor waste management and water wastage on climate change. Such awareness can create a new culture of avoiding behaviours and practices that add to the global warming problem, which will inevitably increase the buy-in to the adoption of the climate change SDG at industry level.

Financing of climate change mitigation projects should be made available to cater for the financial challenge that has been a big cause or slow adoption by industry. The UN or any other relevant body can craft a feasible method of applying the polluter pays principle at a global level and create a pool of funds from fines paid by emitters of greenhouse gases which can then be availed to developing countries to finance mitigation and adaptation projects. This will not only provide funding for developing nations but will also discourage emissions.

5.1.4 Conclusions

Before 2015, there was no consensus globally in urgently addressing the climate change problem. Though it was a topical issue in some countries and in debates held by scientists in developed nations, a clear strategy with actions for addressing its

impacts and seriousness was never discussed at a global level. The SDGs began a new era of global collaboration to act on the challenges that humanity face with urgency. In spite of the sceptics who continue to argue against the possibility of human contribution to global warming, the voices of the proponents of climate change mitigation are getting louder and the world is starting to act.

Climate change is not a topical issue in the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare. As a result, it is often dealt with in an attempt to address sustainability and environmental management. The extent and manner of implementation of environmental management initiatives have proven effective by and large. Although in certain respects, the problem lies with enforcement, evidence shows that the voluntary environmental protection initiatives are a testament of industry's willingness to adopt to the climate change SDG.

5.2 Recommendations

Zimbabwe's GHG emissions are believed to be low in comparison to bigger developed nations. Actually, the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare is said to emit insignificant amounts of GHG into the atmosphere. However, this does not preclude the industry from adopting the climate change SDG, particularly given the national agenda to transform the economy into an upper middle-income society by 2030. There are positive steps that are being taken, such as the adoption of voluntary environmental management and sustainability programs by industry. It is based on issues raised in this dissertation that recommendations are presented below.

The agricultural manufacturing industry in Harare can play an essential role in delivering the information people need to participate in the debates and decisions about climate change and how it affects their lives, with the aim of getting all stakeholders involved.

A. Funding

International funding organisations and governments should create a financing pool to assist industry with affordable finances in the form of loans for introducing climate change mitigation projects. These funds can be built from carbon tax levied on all manufacturing companies in Zimbabwe.

B. Actions plans

Expand policy documents to actions broken down by industry sector and introduce practical measures of monitoring and evaluating the implementation of these action plans. Government led industry workshops to disseminate these action steps should be conducted and post introduction seminars held to assess progress and discuss any bottlenecks. There should be close collaboration between policy makers and captains of industry to discuss challenges in implementation and possible solutions.

C. Incentives

Offer tax incentives to industry to encourage the urgent adoption of the climate change SDG, similar to waivers and rebates given to businesses in developing countries for corporate social responsibility initiatives.

D. Carbon offsetting

Promote the carbon offsetting initiative. Zimbabwe is endowed with vast amounts of arable land countrywide which can be used to plant forests that can be used to offset carbon emissions. Carbon offsets from the forests can be sold to local industries and any excess supply can be sold to other countries thus generating the much needed foreign currency which can be channelled towards the climate change funding pool.

CO₂ emissions will continue to be a problem for as long as fossil fuels are still the main form of energy usage, thereby providing a solution for offsetting the emissions

will go a long way in reducing the amount of CO₂ in the atmosphere. Forests provide a safe and cheap solution for capturing CO₂, together with many other benefits.

E. Further studies

There is a need for further research in the following areas:

- The formation of a separate department in EMA with a focus on disseminating information and monitoring the adoption of the climate change SDG objectives with full capabilities similar to the police.
- The amount of GHG emissions that the agriculture manufacturing industries emit into the atmosphere from their operations. This will help to introduce effective carbon offsetting solutions for each business.

5.3 Conclusion

Though the GHG emissions of the agriculture manufacturing industry in Harare are believed to be low compared to other industries and more developed countries, it is important for industry to adhere to the statues of the country as well as the global agenda to combat climate change and its impacts. As a developing country, Zimbabwe can avoid making the mistakes made by other developing countries in their efforts to become industrialised which have resulted in the climate change crisis.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A

Consent to take part in research

- I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
- I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data from my interview within two weeks after the interview, in which case the material will be deleted.
- I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
- I understand that participation involves a 30 minute interview with the primary researcher.
- I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
- I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
- I understand that in any report on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my interview which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about.
- I understand that disguised extracts from my interview may be quoted in a dissertation and published papers by the primary researcher.

- I understand that if I inform the researcher that myself or someone else is at risk of harm, they may have to report this to the relevant authorities - they will discuss this with me first but may be required to report with or without my permission.

- I understand that signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained in the custody of the researcher until MANCOSA confirms the results of her dissertation.

- I understand that a transcript of my interview in which all identifying information has been removed will be retained for two years from the date of the results being issued.

- I understand that under freedom of information legalisation I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.

- I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

- I agree to my interview being audio-recorded Yes No (*Tick appropriate box*)

Signature of research participant

Signature of participant

Date

Signature of researcher

I believe the participant is giving informed consent to participate in this study

Signature of researcher

Date

Appendix B

21 September 2021

The SHEQ Officer

ATTENTION: MR SHUVAI MUTASA

Dear sir

RE: CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH STUDY

I am grateful for your participation in the study of the “adoption of the climate change SDG goal by the manufacturing industry in Harare”. The study will be a 30 minutes long interview. Please note the interview results and individual results of this study will remain absolutely confidential and anonymous.

Please be as honest and open as you can be in your responses. If I ask a question, you are not comfortable to answer please let me know. I have a schedule of questions to guide me so we can cover all the areas of the study. I will make notes of our discussion as we go along.

With your permission I will also make an audio recording of the interview to assist me to review the discussion at a later stage. The audio will not be shared with anyone and will be disposed of by myself at the end of the study.

If you agree kindly sign the attached consent form, acknowledging your consent and permission for me to conduct this study.

Sincerely,

Geraldine Mupandanyama

Appendix C

Interview guide for SHE Officer/Manager

The success of this research is dependent on building rapport with the participants. Therefore, probes will be used to demonstrate active listening and to collect richer data.

Examples of such probes are:

Can you give me an example of that?"

"Do you have a story about that?"

"Please tell me more,

Opening

My name is Geraldine Mupandanyama, I am an MBA student with MANCOSA. I am conducting a research to establish the adoption of the Climate Change SDG by the manufacturing industry in Harare.

I will not use your name or any other identifying information and everything you say will only be used for research purposes.

I would like to ask you some questions about Climate change and the SDGs. The questions will be centered around your understanding of climate change, your view about the SDGs, what you think should be done to mitigate climate change, the challenges you are facing in executing your role in your company, what your organisation is doing to mitigate climate change, the factors of implementing climate change SDG by businesses, and the strategies that can improve the adoption of the climate change SDG.

I would like to use this information to help the manufacturing industry and society at large to understand the meaning, impact and solutions of climate change in the Zimbabwe context. The interview should take 30 minutes.

Interview guide

Section A: Demographic

What is your age?

What is your job title?

What is your highest qualification?

Section B: Knowledge of the SDGs

1. What does climate change mean to you?
2. What are your views about the SDGs?
3. What about the Climate change SDG?

Section C: Factors of implementing the Climate Change SDG

4. Tell me a story about something that happened at your workplace that reminded you of the climate change problem?
5. What challenges are you facing in executing your environmental management role in your company?
6. What are the factors of implementing the climate change SDG by business?

Section D: Adoption of the Climate Change SDG

7. What comes to your mind when you hear about climate change mitigation and/ or adaptation?
8. What do you think should be done to mitigate climate change?
9. What is your organisation doing to mitigate climate change?

Section E: Strategies that can improve the adoption of the Climate Change SDG

10. What strategies can agriculture manufacturing businesses implement to improve the adoption of the climate change SDG?
11. If you had the power to control the industry's adoption strategies what changes would you make?

12. What would you recommend to maximise the adoption rate?

Appendix D

Themes of findings:

Theme #	Theme	Sub themes from codes
1	Industry awareness of climate change & the Sustainable development goal	Understanding of climate change
		Understanding of the SDGs
2	Zimbabwe's contribution to the climate change problem	How much is Zimbabwe contributing to Climate change
		Public awareness of climate change
3	Environmental management initiatives by industry	Company's environmental impact management programs
		Industry solutions
		Employee training & awareness has an impact
4	Industry challenges and problems regarding climate change mitigation action	Mitigation challenges
5	Regulatory control of climate change	Regulatory control